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Master Thesis

The post-growth funding dilemma of the welfare state: An explorative analysis of the growth dependence of the Austrian welfare state

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Abstract

To expedite a social-ecological transformation, it is necessary to overcome structural growth dependencies that currently lock societies in a spiral of social-ecological crises. This master's thesis thus scrutinises the issue of welfare state growth dependence, which until now has received only minor attention in post-growth literature. Based on a comprehensive literature review, I develop a typology of welfare state growth dependence, delineating four distinct dilemmas: (i) the expenditure dilemma, (ii) the revenue dilemma, (iii) the automatic stabiliser dilemma, and lastly (iv) the post-growth funding dilemma – the latter being the focus of this thesis. In essence, the post-growth funding dilemma arises in a degrowing economy, as the sustainable downscaling of economic activities results in declining welfare state receipts, *ceteris paribus*. I argue that the post-growth funding dilemma is a type of second-order growth dependence grounded in the growth dependencies of those socioeconomic areas used as sources for welfare state funding. I proceed with a political economy analysis of the post-growth funding dilemma, drawing on insights from critical state theory and in particular neo-Marxist accounts of state imperatives. I infer that the post-growth funding dilemma constitutes a latent contradiction of welfare capitalism.

Following an overview of the regime characteristics and expenditures of the Austrian welfare state, I analyse the tax base composition of welfare state funding in Austria with respect to labour, capital, land, and consumption. Subsequently, these socioeconomic areas are subjected to a growth dependence analysis, which leads to a more nuanced restatement of the post-growth funding dilemma. I infer that the growth dependence of employment is the main source of the post-growth funding dilemma. On a more structural level, however, capital as self-expanding value is identified as the main cause of growth dependencies in the capitalist economic system. In the case of the Austrian welfare state, I conclude that its heavy reliance on labour taxes and social contributions constitutes the main cause of its post-growth funding dilemma. Built on the insights developed, I formulate tentative suggestions for policy avenues towards growth independent welfare states. To overcome the post-growth funding dilemma, the following measures are proposed: taxes on various forms of capital; a redistributive reduction of labour taxes and social contributions; measures to tackle the growth dependence of employment (e.g. working time reduction); and taxes on land. The thesis concludes with a discussion of the results and a more encompassing outlook pertaining to the nature of welfare states in a future post-growth society.

Keywords: post-growth, (Austrian) welfare state, growth dependence, welfare state funding, contradiction of capitalism

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The public finances are one of the best starting points for an investigation of society, especially though not exclusively of its political life. The full fruitfulness of this approach is seen particularly at those turning points, or better epochs, during which existing forms begin to die off and to change into something new, and which always involve a crisis of the old fiscal methods.

– Joseph Alois Schumpeter (1918, p. 7)

1. Introduction

How can humanity secure the satisfaction of current and future generations' basic needs whilst safeguarding the ecological integrity of the Earth system? This is probably the most pressing question of our time. Currently, no single country provides the basic social foundations for a good life without transgressing national per capita biophysical boundaries. Generally, countries that perform well in terms of social indicators do so at levels of resource use incompatible with global sustainability requirements, and vice versa (O'Neill et al., 2018). Current development trajectories are expected to further drive ecological deterioration, while failing to deliver large-scale social improvements (Fanning et al., 2022). Moreover, achieving a good life both for current and future generations within an inherently finite natural environment may be a dauntingly challenging task, given that the intersecting space of achieving both global needs satisfaction and environmental sustainability might be “vanishingly thin” (O'Neill et al., 2018, p. 92). Certainly, nothing less than a profound social-ecological transformation of our economy and society is required to meet this challenge. How such a social-ecological transformation may come about and what strategies should be employed to facilitate it is, however, a matter of intense political and scholarly debate (Wissen & Brand, 2017).

Given the hegemonic character of the socio-politically pervasive growth paradigm (Dale, 2012; Schmelzer, 2015), it is quite unsurprising that economic growth itself is oftentimes portrayed as the main remedy to overcome the manifold social, economic and environmental predicaments of modern capitalist societies. During the second half of the 20th century, economic growth – i.e. the recurring increase of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) – has come to be associated with development, progress, as well as modernisation and is thus commonly portrayed as the main vehicle for increasing social welfare (Schmelzer, 2015). Moreover, economic growth is oftentimes put forward as a panacea for a myriad of socioeconomic issues such as inequality, poverty, and

unemployment (Dale, 2012; Schmelzer, 2015; Welzer, 2011). Most recently, the intensifying social-ecological crisis has prompted a green reconstruction of the growth paradigm. In the last decade, the notion of (inclusive) green growth – and the related idea of a green economy – have come to dominate environmental policy discourses (OECD, 2011; UNEP, 2011; World Bank, 2012). One of the latest and politically most tangible manifestations of the green growth discourse is the European Green Deal. In the opening lines of its official communication, the European Green Deal is described as

“a new growth strategy that aims to **transform the EU into a fair and prosperous society, with a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy** where there are **no net emissions of greenhouse gases in 2050 and where economic growth is decoupled from resource use**” (European Commission, 2019, p. 2, emphasis in original).

There are, however, at least three reasons to call into question the socioeconomic desirability as well as the economic and ecological feasibility of economic growth as the *modus operandi* of the current socioeconomic system, especially in the high-income countries of the Global North. First of all, economic growth and related increases in income do not necessarily translate into improved individual happiness in the long term (Easterlin, 2015; Easterlin et al., 2010). Or as Latouche (2009, p. 22) wittily asserts, “if growth automatically generated wellbeing we would now be living in paradise”. Easterlin (1974) maintains that this seeming paradox results from the fact that individuals’ happiness is largely determined by relative status considerations, rather than income in absolute terms. People tend to evaluate their happiness with regard to a given standard of living that is perceived as the pervasive social norm¹. As this standard of living, however, tends to rise with economic growth, continuous increases in real income become necessary to even retain a given level of happiness. In that regard, growth-centred societies may be locked in a “hedonic treadmill” (Brickman & Campbell, 1971; Büchs & Koch, 2017). Secondly, the secular stagnation hypothesis² suggests that economic growth rates might continue to decline – especially in high-income countries – eventually leading to long-term economic stagnation in terms of GDP growth (R. J. Gordon, 2012; Hein, 2015; Jackson, 2019; Scarano, 2017; Summers, 2014; Teulings &

¹ The relativity of subjective happiness has already been pointed out by Karl Marx (2020, p. 33) in his writings: “A house may be large or small; as long as the surrounding houses are equally small it satisfies all social demands for a dwelling. But let a palace arise beside the little house, and it shrinks from a little house to a hut. The little house shows now that its owner has only very slight or no demands to make; and however high it may shoot up in the course of civilization, if the neighbouring palace grows to an equal or even greater extent, the occupant of the relatively small house will feel more and more uncomfortable, dissatisfied and cramped within its four walls”.

² Mainstream and heterodox economists offer quite different explanations regarding the causes of secular stagnation. For an instructive discussion, see Parrique (2019).

Baldwin, 2014). Thirdly, a myriad of scholars calls into question the main premise of green growth, namely that environmental sustainability is reconcilable with continuous economic growth via an absolute decoupling of economic growth from resource use and environmental impacts (Hickel & Kallis, 2019; Jackson, 2016; Kallis et al., 2018; Parrique et al., 2019; Haberl et al., 2020; Wiedenhofer et al., 2020). Essentially, it follows from the laws of thermodynamics that energy-based economic growth is subject to inherent limits thus constraining the scale of economic production and consumption (Georgescu-Roegen, 1975; Mayumi, 2017). To stay within planetary boundaries and thus safeguard the integrity of the Earth system (Steffen et al., 2015), the current trajectory and political pursuit of continuous economic growth has to be abandoned. What is thus required is a social-ecological transformation grounded in notions of sufficiency and post-growth to achieve a good life for all within biophysical limits (Fanning et al., 2022; O'Neill et al., 2018).

1.1 The post-growth transformation: Overcoming structural growth dependencies

The notion of a fundamental social-ecological transformation that transcends the hegemony of the growth paradigm has been articulated in a number of different – and sometimes contesting – ways (Büchs & Koch, 2017; Daly, 1996; Ferguson, 2013; Jackson, 2016; Kallis et al., 2018; Latouche, 2009; Paech, 2012; Perkins, 2007; Spash, 2020; van den Bergh, 2011; Victor, 2008). Being located at the intersection of social-ecological economics (Spash, 2012, 2017, 2020) and eco-Marxism (Burkett, 2006; Foster, 2002; O'Connor, 1998), my master's thesis is based on a *post-growth* conception of the social-ecological transformation³. In a nutshell, the post-growth position advanced here posits that staying within planetary boundaries and enabling current and future generations to satisfy their basic needs can *only* be achieved if societies first overcome growth imperatives and structural growth dependencies⁴, thus enabling them to drastically reduce their material and energetic throughput without pernicious socioeconomic consequences⁵. From a

³ Regarding terminology, I prefer the term 'post-growth' over the closely related term of 'degrowth'. First, the 'post' prefix accurately indicates and communicates the need go *beyond* the primate of economic growth (Strunz & Schindler, 2018) and hence overcome the growth dependencies in the socioeconomic system that currently inhibit societies to expedite a social-ecological transformation. Secondly, the term degrowth may be disadvantageous for the purpose of communicating a social-ecological transformation to a broader public audience, as its prefix implies a downward orientation. This might lead to unfavourable evaluations of degrowth, either through the unconscious association with negative feelings or due to misinterpretations that link degrowth to economic recessions (Drews & Antal, 2016).

⁴ The overcoming of growth dependencies also seems to be a reasonable socio-political ambition in a growth-based economic system, as it would decrease the negative impacts of economic downturns and recessions on socioeconomic institutions and society at large. In that regard, Loske (2018) argues that the reduction of growth dependencies might be a common issue for both post-growth and mainstream economists to work on.

⁵ Both post-growth and degrowth scholars sometimes embrace an a-growth position in their writings (Jackson, 2016; Latouche, 2009; Petschow et al., 2018a; Seidl & Zahrt, 2010a; Strunz & Schindler, 2018; Victor, 2008), that is the proposition that societies should be indifferent or agnostic about economic growth in order to make social-ecological policies politically feasible (van den Bergh, 2011). My conception of post-growth, however, explicitly rejects this a-growth proposition. Growth-indifference is an insufficient political strategy to achieve a social-ecological

global justice perspective, it must be emphasised here that the high-income countries of the Global North carry the main responsibility in reducing the extent of their economic activities and adapting their social metabolisms to the sustainability requirements implied by planetary boundaries⁶ (Fanning et al., 2022; Hickel et al., 2022).

The post-growth position advanced in this thesis is in a sense eclectic, as it reflects and combines insights both from the abundant literature on degrowth as well as from the discourse on 'Postwachstum' prevalent in German-speaking countries⁷. With respect to the former, Schneider et al. (2010, p. 512) offer the following definition: "Sustainable degrowth may be defined as an equitable downscaling of production and consumption that increases human well-being and enhances ecological conditions at the local and global level, in the short and long term". Moreover, degrowth scholars emphasise that the implied social-ecological transformation must be democratically governed and further ought to entail a deepening and renewal of democratic institutions and processes (Asara et al., 2013; Cattaneo et al., 2012; Deriu, 2012; Hausknost, 2017; Strunz & Bartkowski, 2018). Last but not least, decoloniality and feminism (Abazeri, 2022; Dengler & Seebacher, 2019; Löw, 2015) are put forward as integral aspects of degrowth, in the sense that the implied social-ecological transformation must be "sensitive to patriarchal gender relations, colonial continuities and economic structures that enable and (re-)produce these relations" (Dengler & Seebacher, 2019, p. 251).

The Postwachstum discourse in German-speaking countries is unique due to the special consideration of growth imperatives and growth dependencies as inhibitors of structural changes towards sustainability (Lange, 2018). According to Rosa (2018, p. 54), "modern societies are characterised by the fact that they can only reproduce their institutional structures dynamically, i.e. in an escalatory mode of growth, acceleration and innovation". This feature of modern societies is particularly pronounced in capitalist economies and gives rise to their growth dependence (Rosa

transformation, since the existence of structural growth dependencies implies that our socioeconomic institutions necessitate economic growth for their continued stability and reproduction. Hence, an a-growth strategy alone cannot enable societies to implement the required social-ecological policies but will rather – even if inadvertently – sustain our growth-centred society that gives rise to social-ecological crises. Similarly to Haapanen & Tapio (2016), I argue that for societies to be truly indifferent about economic growth first requires the overcoming of growth dependencies and thus post-growth. In other words, a-growth will be the corollary of post-growth and the related social-ecological transformation, not the other way around.

⁶ Authors such as Kerschner (2010) and Jackson (2016) argue that degrowth in the Global North is required in order to make room for economic growth in the Global South. From a post-development perspective, Spash (2020) rightly objects to this notion, as it reproduces the idea that economic growth corresponds to economic development and is thus an essential means to poverty alleviation.

⁷ Lehmann et al. (2022) provide an instructive overview of the different concepts dealing with the role of economic growth with respect to environmental sustainability.

et al., 2017). Contemporary capitalist institutions and socioeconomic structures drive, depend on, and systematically necessitate economic growth as the societal *modus operandi* (Petschow et al., 2018a; Richters & Siemoneit, 2019; Seidl & Zahrnt, 2012; Stratford, 2020). Hence, the overcoming of structural growth dependencies is seen as a prerequisite for realising a post-growth transformation. In that regard, Postwachstum scholars put particular emphasis on those structural and political barriers that hinder the implementation of policies that prioritise human needs satisfaction and environmental sustainability over economic growth (Paech, 2006; Petschow et al., 2018a; Rosa, 2016; Seidl & Zahrnt, 2012; Strunz & Schindler, 2018; Welzer, 2011).

Moreover, the issue of growth dependence is also rooted in the political economy of welfare capitalism. According to Hausknost (2020), the state's ability to implement adequate sustainability measures is inherently inhibited by existing state imperatives, particularly the imperative of economic growth as well as the imperative of democratic legitimation, the latter entailing the provisioning of welfare through the democratic welfare state (Offe, 1984a). Hausknost (2020, p. 22) thus argues that a post-growth transformation “would tend to openly contradict the functional requirements of the state, as measures that lead to reductions in consumption, production and – by implication – employment and state revenue are toxic for all but the sustainability imperative”.

Based on these considerations, it becomes apparent that a social-ecological transformation towards a post-growth economy is inhibited by an intricate interplay between the capitalist logic of expansion on the one hand, and the obligations of the democratic state to facilitate capital accumulation while simultaneously providing welfare to its citizens on the other. Hence, fundamental changes to the contemporary economic institutions and the social imaginaries are required to transcend the structural growth dependencies that currently lock societies in an ostensibly escalatory spiral of multidimensional economic, social, and ecological crises. It is here that contemporary welfare states find themselves in the midst of a fundamental predicament between the perpetuation of the current mode of dynamic stabilisation and the necessity for a profound social-ecological transformation. As we will see, this predicament may materialise in the form of pronounced fiscal dilemmas for the welfare state.

1.2 The fiscal predicaments of welfare states

Most generally speaking, welfare states can be seen as socioeconomic institutions concerned with the satisfaction of certain needs, the redistribution of wealth and income, and the provision of

insurance against risks across the life cycle (Barr, 2001; Greve, 2019; Kuhlmann, 2018; Titmuss, 1959). As a vehicle for social amelioration and a regulatory instance within the political economy of capitalist economies (Esping-Andersen, 1990), welfare states surely represent one of the major societal achievements of the 20th century. The welfare state is an essential, however, politically contested and continuously evolving feature of modern capitalist economies (Garland, 2014).

Following the so-called golden age of the welfare state after World War II, which was characterised by an expansion and deepening of social policies in the Western world⁸, welfare states entered into a period of retrenchment and restructuring from the mid 1970s onwards (Corlet Walker et al., 2021; Esping-Andersen, 1996; Kuhlmann et al., 2016; Levy, 2021; Nullmeier & Kaufmann, 2021; Pierson, 2007). In the aftermath of the 2007/08 financial crisis and the subsequently unfolding Great Recession, rising national debt levels and considerable budgetary deficits compelled governments worldwide to pursue fiscal consolidation via expenditure cuts⁹ (Ortiz et al., 2015). In the case of Europe, states came under substantial pressures to cut back on public spending due to the spectre of a fiscal crisis (Farnsworth & Irving, 2018), which resulted in the implementation of austerity packages and hence substantive welfare state retrenchment across the continent (Schubert et al., 2016; Taylor-Gooby et al., 2017).

Recently, the COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the significance of welfare states as vital institutions for crisis management (Béland, Cantillon, et al., 2021), with social policy responses being grounded in a mode of “emergency Keynesianism” (Bremer & McDaniel, 2020, p. 439). Governments’ COVID-19 response measures were, however, financed via deficits and thus resulted in increasing government debt levels (Makin & Layton, 2021). While governments’ crisis management in the early onset of the COVID-19 pandemic seem to have not been decisively affected by debt considerations¹⁰, the issue of government debt may once again come to be a determining political factor for the quality and extent of social policies in the future: “A new politics of welfare may emerge, but it may not be one of our choosing” (Moreira & Hick, 2021, p. 276). As government expenditures repeatedly outrun the revenues raised, the (welfare) state may

⁸ The golden age of the welfare state coincided with the golden age of economic growth in the Western world in the post-war years (Crafts, 1995; Vonyó, 2008). In that regard, Gough (2021, p. 913) asserts that “it is no coincidence that the post-war welfare state emerged simultaneously with the modern tax state and growth state”.

⁹ An alternative approach, of course, would have been for governments to consolidate their state budgets via raising extra revenue, for instance through increasing taxes. In Europe, expenditure cuts were, however, the more common crisis response, while measures aiming to raise revenue remained rather limited (Theodoropoulou & Watt, 2011).

¹⁰ In the EU-27, the enactment of expansionary fiscal measures to counteract the socioeconomic impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic was facilitated by the activation of the general escape clause of the Stability and Growth Pact in March 2020.

face yet another substantial fiscal crisis (Farnsworth & Irving, 2018), which could challenge the scope of social policies and the integrity of the contemporary welfare state in general. Fiscal austerity, however, does not seem to be a socially desirable response to reduce government debt levels, as it is associated with rising inequalities, lower incomes as well as long-term increases in unemployment (Ball, Leigh, Furceri, et al., 2013).

The ongoing ecological crisis adds yet another dimension to the intricate issues with which welfare states are currently confronted. The multidimensional dynamics of environmental change will give rise to new climate-related risks and inequalities, while affecting vulnerable communities and households most severely (IPCC, 2022). The ecological crisis thus increases the need for a functioning welfare state in general and eco-social policies in particular to facilitate a just transition towards a sustainable economic system (Bailey, 2015; Bohnenberger, 2020; Gough, 2017; Hirvilammi, 2020; Koch, 2021).

Paradoxically, however, extensive welfare state arrangements may be both part of the solution as well as a major contributing factor to the dynamics that drive the ecological crisis. Due to their embeddedness into the capitalist state and economic system, welfare states are inherently dependent on continuous economic growth in order to maintain their functionality (Bailey, 2015; Büchs, 2021; Corlet Walker et al., 2021; Hirvilammi, 2020; Hirvilammi & Koch, 2020; Laurent, 2021; Opielka, 2017; Petschow et al., 2018a; Quilley & Zywert, 2019; Seidl & Zahrnt, 2010b). As will become apparent in the course of this thesis, the welfare state's dependence on economic growth is essentially a *fiscal* growth dependence, as it currently depends on the continuous expansion of economic activities to generate sufficient revenues to fund its expenditures. In that regard, Bailey (2015) contends that the fiscal sustainability of the welfare state is indirectly predicated upon an environmentally destructive mode of economic expansion. To re-appropriate Claus Offe's (1984b) famous dictum, capitalist economies and their modes of democratic legitimation are now faced with an *ecological* crisis of crisis management.

Building on the normative assumption that welfare states are socio-politically desirable institutions that should be preserved as an essential element of democratic societies, the question arises how the growth dependence of welfare states can be overcome. It is here that societies are confronted with an intricate predicament, which Bailey (2015, p. 795, emphasis in original) succinctly captures:

“If we are to reduce levels of (taxable) economic activity as post-growth theorists suggest, we *ceteris paribus* threaten the public sector funding base of welfare states and impede the state’s traditional mechanisms of ‘crisis management’. Simultaneously, the welfare state is required more so than ever in what could be a tumultuous transitional period, not only in terms of protecting society’s poorest and most vulnerable but also in terms of facilitating decarbonisation attempts and providing efficient modes of insuring against a confluence of socio-economic and environmental risks”.

A social-ecological transformation from a post-growth perspective hence requires the decoupling of welfare states’ functionality and funding from economic growth. In other words, the challenge is to ensure the fiscal sustainability of the welfare state within a degrowing economy¹¹ without reverting to socioeconomically pernicious forms of welfare state retrenchment. Indeed, the social-ecological crisis and the necessity of a post-growth transformation may signify one of “those turning points, or better epochs, during which existing forms begin to die off and to change into something new, and which always involve a crisis of the old fiscal methods” (Schumpeter, 1918, p. 7). Reformulating Schumpeter’s epigraph, I hence contend that public finances are one of the best starting points for an investigation into both the potential and the challenges pertaining to the realisation of a democratic post-growth society and a welfare state beyond growth.

1.3 Research question and structure of the thesis

Within this context, I seek to scrutinise the intricate issue of growth dependence by analysing the concrete example of the Austrian welfare state. I thus formulate the following research question: In what ways and to what extent does the funding structure of the Austrian welfare state and its welfare programmes result in a dependence on economic growth? This master’s thesis hence addresses one of the five dilemmas of post-growth welfare systems identified by Corlet Walker et al. (2021), namely how to fund welfare states within the context of a non-growing economy. This is what I shall call the *post-growth funding dilemma* of the welfare state.

The welfare state remains an under-researched subject matter in sustainability research. Strunz & Schindler (2018) contend that the issue of welfare state provisioning has only received minor attention within the post-growth literature. Similarly, Helne & Hirvilammi (2019, p. 225f.) maintain

¹¹ I use the term ‘degrowing economy’ to refer to a non-growing or contracting economy in the sense of Schneider et al.’s (2010) definition of degrowth. In that regard, degrowth refers to the requisite transformative process taking place in a transition towards a post-growth society that transcends the primacy of the growth paradigm. It must be emphasised that a degrowing economy is hence inherently dissimilar to an economic recession occurring within a growth-based economic system.

that “the degrowth discussion has partly skipped over the magnitude of policy-level challenges and has perhaps therefore underestimated the tasks ahead for the welfare states whose institutions have been developed side by side with capitalist accumulation and economic growth”. It thus seems as though the growth dependence of the welfare state is a highly topical issue for post-growth scholars. Despite the societal and academic relevance of this issue, an integrated analysis of welfare states’ dependence on economic growth is currently missing in the literature. Giving an extensive literature overview of climate-social policies, Bohnenberger (2022) notes that the growth dependence of the welfare states remains an only rudimentarily developed field of research. It is thus the aim of this master’s thesis to contribute to the literature and address the insinuated research gap in post-growth welfare state research by analysing how the funding modes of the Austrian welfare state give rise to its ostensible growth dependence. As Lange & Jackson (2019) emphasise, such a country-specific analysis of welfare states’ growth dependence is crucial to properly identify the specific transformative actions required as well as potential obstacles to realising growth independent welfare states.

Given the sparse state of the literature on welfare state growth dependence, the analysis attempted in this master’s thesis must certainly be of an exploratory character. Nonetheless, I believe that the insights developed can help to shed light on some remaining blind spots in this important field of research and highlight promising avenues for future investigation. Moreover, the analysis may point towards possible leverage points for decreasing the growth dependence of welfare states, with the aim of ensuring welfare state provisioning in degrowing economies and thus a socially just transformation towards an economic system able to operate within planetary boundaries.

My master’s thesis is structured as follows. First, section 2 gives an overview of the state of the literature on welfare state growth dependence. Here, I develop a basic typology of welfare state growth dependence, distinguishing between four dilemmas of welfare state growth dependence. I then explore these four dilemmas separately. In section 3, I analyse the post-growth funding dilemma from a political economy perspective by drawing on critical state theory, and in particular neo-Marxist accounts of state imperatives. In essence, I maintain that the post-growth funding dilemma can be seen as a latent contradiction of welfare capitalism. In section 4, I turn to the analysis of the Austrian welfare state. After substantiating the choice of the Austrian welfare state as my case study subject, I briefly explore the concept of the welfare state and make some terminological clarifications. I then proceed with an overview of the Austrian welfare state, its institutional characteristics, and expenditures. In section 5, the main argument of this thesis is

developed. First, I explore the funding composition of the Austrian welfare state. Thereafter, I explore how and to which extent the socioeconomic areas relevant for welfare state funding are themselves subject to growth dependencies. The section concludes with a restatement of the post-growth funding dilemma and a discussion of its manifestation in the case of the Austrian welfare state. Based on the insights developed, I then draw some tentative conclusions on potential policy avenues towards growth independent welfare states in section 6. In the concluding section of this master's thesis, I give a brief synopsis of my analysis and engage in a broader discussion of my results, covering limitations, avenues for further research and an outlook on welfare states beyond growth.

2. Literature review: Looking for the growth dependence of the welfare state

This master's thesis is situated within the research field of *sustainable welfare*. In broad terms, the sustainable welfare literature investigates interdependent issues emerging “at the intersection of social policy, welfare states, and environmental issues” (Hirvilammi & Koch, 2020, p. 2). A subject of major concern for the sustainable welfare literature is the establishment of welfare (state) systems able to guarantee basic need satisfaction without transgressing planetary boundaries, accompanied by a deprioritisation of economic growth as a socio-political goal (Büchs, 2021; Büchs & Koch, 2017; Hirvilammi & Koch, 2020; Koch, 2018). As such, the sustainable welfare literature is also closely connected to discourses around degrowth and post-growth.

Particular emphasis within the sustainable welfare literature¹² is oftentimes put on the issue of eco-social policies that seek to satisfy basic needs in an environmentally sustainable manner (Bohnenberger, 2020; Fitzpatrick & Cahill, 2002; Gough, 2015a, 2017, 2019; Koch, 2018, 2021; Koch & Mont, 2016; Lindellee et al., 2021; Stamm et al., 2020), the social and distributional impacts of environmental policy implementation (Büchs et al., 2014; Gough, 2013), the emergence of new social risks arising due to the ecological crisis (Gough, 2017; Johansson et al., 2016) as well as issues surrounding the notion of environmental and eco-social states, respectively (Fritz & Koch, 2014; Gough, 2016; Hausknost, 2020; Koch, 2020; Meadowcroft, 2012). Furthermore, sustainable welfare scholars oftentimes stress the pivotal role of welfare states in facilitating an ecological

¹² Bohnenberger (2022) provides a highly instructive overview of different issues investigated in this broad research field.

transformation of the economy in a socially just manner (Bailey, 2015; Bohnenberger, 2020; Gough, 2019; Hirvilammi, 2020).

Sustainable welfare scholars also touch upon and acknowledge issues emerging from the interdependence of economic growth and welfare states (Büchs, 2021). In that regard, Corlet Walker et al. (2021) assert the emergence of a closely connected, however, distinct strand of research concerned with *welfare systems without economic growth*. Here, the growth dependence of the welfare state and the underlying causes represent central issues of concern. Essentially, a transformation towards a post-growth economy requires a reduction and indeed an overcoming of structural growth dependencies. Accordingly, Büchs (2021, p. 1) states that “one of the main challenges of sustainable welfare is to design welfare systems that are ‘growth resilient’ or independent of economic growth”. It is this challenge that this master’s thesis seeks to address.

2.1 A typology of welfare state growth dependence

The issue of welfare states’ growth dependence has recently received increasing consideration within discourses surrounding sustainable welfare and post-growth (Bailey, 2015; Büchs, 2021; Büchs & Koch, 2017; Corlet Walker et al., 2021; Gough & Meadowcroft, 2011; Hirvilammi, 2020; Hirvilammi & Koch, 2020; Koch, 2021; Kubon-Gilke, 2021; Laurent, 2021; Opielka, 2017; Parrique, 2019; Petschow et al., 2018a; Quilley & Zywert, 2019; Seidl & Zahrt, 2010b; Wiedmann et al., 2020). To scrutinise the issue of welfare state growth dependence, the definition of growth dependence advanced by Petschow et al., (2018b, p. 13) is instructive:

“By growth-dependent areas, we mean those social systems, structures or institutions, (a) that fulfil a socially desirable function or contribute to a socially widely accepted goal and (b) whose socially acceptable functionality or contribution under current framework conditions depends on a continuously growing economy”.

In short, a given socioeconomic area or social subsystem can be defined as growth dependent if its socio-politically desired functionality is contingent on continuous economic growth. The growth dependence of a given area or institution thus implies that a lack of economic growth necessarily results in substantial social or economic repercussions on the individual and/or societal level.

With respect to the welfare state, the nature of this growth dependence as well as the dynamics from which it originates are, however, still only insufficiently understood and conceptualised in the literature. Moreover, basic analytical distinctions regarding the nature of welfare states' growth dependence are currently missing. Based on a comprehensive literature review, I suggest a parsimonious typology of welfare state growth dependence to delineate more accurately the dynamics and phenomena that give rise to welfare states' dependence on economic growth. In that regard, a good starting point is a perspective of accounting, as intimated by Bailey (2015) and Corlet Walker et al. (2021). This accounting perspective is in line with a basic notion of public finance: Given the extent of public expenditures in relation to public revenues, governments can either run a deficit, surplus or a balanced budget (Khan, 2019). Applying this line of thinking to the issue of funding the welfare state, the following equation¹³ – characterising a fiscally balanced funding of a welfare state – can serve as a mental starting point and useful heuristic to better conceptualise welfare state growth dependence, its different drivers, and manifestations.

$$\textit{Funding of the Welfare State} = \textit{Total Expenditure of the Welfare State} \quad (1.1)$$

Building on this equation, a welfare state can be said to be growth dependent whenever economic growth is a necessary condition for the funding to be equal to or higher than the total expenditure of the welfare state in the medium- to long-run, *ceteris paribus*¹⁴. In that regard, the growth dependence of the welfare state is essentially a *fiscal* growth dependence. Currently, all existing welfare states are growth dependent by design given their embeddedness within the growth-centred, capitalist economic system. A growth independent welfare state, on the other hand, would have to be able to fund its total expenditure in the medium- to long-run in the context of a non-growing or degrowing economy, without reverting to the repeated employment of deficit financing. In other words, a growth independent welfare state necessitates fiscally balanced budgets and surpluses for funding, respectively, to retain its long-term functionality – i.e. the provision of welfare services and programmes to a socio-politically desired extent – in an environment of no economic growth¹⁵.

¹³ A more sophisticated variant of this equation can be found in Cichon et al. (2004, p. 220f.), who assert that a social protection scheme “is in financial equilibrium if the present value of all future expenditure plus the initial reserve $t=0$ is equal to the present value of all future income of the scheme at a given point in time”.

¹⁴ Crucially, with the *ceteris paribus* assumption the extent of welfare state programmes is assumed to be given (at least in the short-term), thus precluding the option of welfare state retrenchment to achieve fiscal balance.

¹⁵ It should be noted that welfare state expenditures may of course be financed via public borrowing (Obinger, 2021; Schmitt et al., 2020). My argument, however, builds on the premise that large-scale deficit financing does not represent a feasible option for funding welfare states in the context of a post-growth economy due to the corollary accumulation of government debt. The issue is further elaborated and discussed in section 7.3.

Let us now take a more disaggregated look at the above equation, starting with the funding side. Welfare state programmes can be financed via taxes and social contributions or a combination of these funding modes¹⁶ (Cichon et al., 2004; Manow, 2010; Morel & Palme, 2018; Obinger, 2021; Schmitt et al., 2020). Building on the delineation of drivers of growth dependence¹⁷ advanced by Corlet Walker & Jackson (2021), the disaggregation on the expenditure side follows the economically intuitive (however simplified) notion that total welfare state expenditure is equal to the demand for welfare state services times the respective costs of their provision¹⁸. Given these considerations, we thus arrive at the following equation able to illuminate how the growth dependence of the welfare state may arise due to different dynamics and phenomena pertaining to the individual variables.

$$\textit{Taxes} + \textit{Social Contributions} = \textit{Demand} \times \textit{Costs} \quad (1.2)$$

Based on this equation, I will distinguish between four types of welfare state growth dependence which – in reference to Corlet Walker et al. (2021) – I refer to as dilemmas of welfare state growth dependence. In a nutshell, all of these dilemmas arise due to societal dynamics that potentially generate fiscal imbalances between the funding and expenditure side of the welfare state and may hence result in fiscal deficits. The four dilemmas are (i) the expenditure dilemma, (ii) the revenue dilemma (iii) the automatic stabiliser dilemma and (iv) the post-growth funding dilemma.

A first overview of these four dilemmas is presented in table 1. The table presents an outline of the processes and dynamics that give rise to the respective dilemmas as well as an indication which side of the welfare state financing equation is affected. Moreover, the dilemmas can be distinguished with respect to the order of growth dependence. In the remainder of this chapter, the four dilemmas of welfare state growth dependence and their underlying societal dynamics will be described in detail.

¹⁶ Schmitt et al. (2020) and Cichon et al. (2004) also identify private and occupational payments as relevant funding sources. Since my analysis, however, focuses on the funding of *public* welfare programmes, these modes of funding are not of primary concern here.

¹⁷ In their study on adult social care in the United Kingdom, Corlet Walker & Jackson (2021) identify rising demand, rising costs, and rent-seeking as core processes driving welfare state growth dependence.

¹⁸ Certainly, welfare state provisioning also entails administrative and bureaucratic costs. These costs, however, will not be further considered in the course of my analysis.

Table 1: The four dilemmas of welfare state growth dependence

Dilemma	Constitutive processes & dynamics	Funding < Expenditure	Order of growth dependence
Expenditure dilemma	<i>Demand-driven:</i> - Demographic change - Ecological crisis - Expectations and conception of wellbeing <i>Cost-driven:</i> - Baumol's cost disease - Technological improvements - Rent-seeking and profit-maximising behaviour	Funding < Expenditure↑	First-order growth dependence
Revenue dilemma	- Demographic change - Rent-seeking and rentier power	Funding↓ < Expenditure	First-order growth dependence
Automatic stabiliser dilemma	Countercyclical operation of the welfare state	Funding↓ ≤ Expenditure↑	First-order growth dependence
Post-growth funding dilemma	Growth dependence of tax bases relevant for welfare state funding	Funding↓ ≤ Expenditure	Second-order growth dependence

Note: Own representation. A second-order growth dependence describes a type of growth dependence that itself arises due to growth dependencies of socioeconomic areas (e.g. employment). Conversely, a first-order growth dependence arises due to dynamics and phenomenon other than growth dependence. The distinction will be further elaborated in section 2.5.

2.2 The expenditure dilemma

Within the sustainable welfare and post-growth literature, scholars oftentimes ascribe welfare states' growth dependence to increasing expenditure levels. This variant of welfare state growth dependence is what I shall call the *expenditure dilemma*. Here, one can further distinguish between dynamics that (i) drive the demand for welfare state services and those that (ii) increase the costs of welfare state provisioning¹⁹.

Starting with the demand-led variant of the expenditure dilemma, one of the most prominently discussed causes of welfare states' growth dependence is demographic change (Bailey, 2015; Büchs, 2021; Corlet Walker et al., 2021; Corlet Walker & Jackson, 2021; Höpflinger, 2010; Kubon-Gilke, 2021; Petschow et al., 2018a; Seidl & Zahrt, 2012; Strunz & Schindler, 2018). Old-age dependency ratios are rising and projected to double in most G20 countries until 2060. This trend will most likely increase the demand for health and (long-term) care services and furthermore raises the number of retirees, thus posing serious issues for the financing of welfare state services, especially

¹⁹ Here, I confine myself to the discussion of those welfare state expenditure drivers discussed within the literature on welfare state growth dependence. The overview of expenditure-driving dynamics is thus not complete.

in times of low economic growth (Rouzet et al., 2019). In their analysis of the German social security system for pension and health insurance, Petschow et al. (2018a) identify demographic changes and the trend of rising life expectancy as major factors contributing to welfare states' growth dependence. On a similar stance, Strunz & Schindler (2018) assert that economic growth is currently necessary to deal with the implications of demographic change for contemporary pension schemes. Bailey (2015) hence rightly contends that the trend of an ageing society fundamentally complicates a transformation towards a post-growth economy with a functioning welfare system.

A second dynamic driving the demand for welfare state services is the multidimensional ecological crisis itself (Bailey, 2015; Bohnenberger, 2020; Gough, 2017; Hirvilammi, 2020; Koch, 2021). The degradation of ecosystems, biodiversity loss, environmental pollution, and extreme weather events have adverse effects on people's physical and mental health, hence giving rise to new social risks, which inevitably affect vulnerable communities and individuals most gravely. Moreover, the ecological crisis and its manifold manifestations do and will lead to increased patterns of cross-regional displacements (IPCC, 2022). It must also be emphasised that urgently needed climate change mitigation policies are oftentimes regressive in nature and thus necessitate further social policies to offset the corollary distributional impacts (Gough, 2013). In that regard, the ecological crisis and its socioeconomic impacts on human livelihoods certainly increase the need for a functioning welfare state and well-crafted eco-social policies.

Lastly, people's expectations for continuously improving wellbeing and health outcomes drive demand for welfare state provisioning, particularly in the domain of health care (Büchs & Koch, 2019; Corlet Walker et al., 2021). In that regard, a welfare state system grounded in a hedonic and thus wants-based understanding of wellbeing may well contribute to increasing demands for welfare state provisioning, since wants – in contrast to needs – are essentially insatiable (Büchs & Koch, 2017; Doyal & Gough, 1991; Gough, 2015b).

Let us now turn to those phenomena that give rise to the expenditure dilemma due to cost-increasing dynamics. Here, a contributing cause of welfare states' growth dependence pertains to the growing relative costs of welfare provisioning (Opielka, 2017; Petschow et al., 2018a), which Corlet Walker et al. (2021) denote as one of five dilemmas of welfare systems without economic growth. One of the main drivers of these relative costs is the phenomenon commonly referred to as Baumol's cost disease, which suggests that if the labour productivity growth of the

manufacturing sector continuously exceeds that of the services sector, then the costs of services increase relative to those of manufactured goods (Baumol, 2012; Helland & Tabarrok, 2019). With respect to the welfare state, Baumol's cost disease has been put forward as a significant driver of health expenditure (Clements et al., 2012; European Commission, 2013). Since the welfare state provides public services, e.g. in the domain of health, care, and education, Baumol's cost disease may jeopardise the fiscal sustainability of the welfare state through increasing expenditure levels (Andersen & Kreiner, 2017).

Secondly, Petschow et al. (2018a) identify technological improvements as a contributing factor to welfare states' growth dependence in terms of the expenditure dilemma. This phenomenon is of particular importance in the health care sector, where technological innovations and advances (e.g. the development of new drugs, medication and medical equipment) represent the main driver of costs and growing health care expenditures (Dybczak & Przywa, 2010; European Commission, 2013).

Another phenomenon contributing to increasing costs pertains to profit-maximising behaviour and rent-seeking²⁰ resulting from the involvement of private actors in the provisioning of welfare state services (Corlet Walker et al., 2021; Corlet Walker & Jackson, 2021). Borowy & Aillon (2017) argue that the financial incentive structures in the health care sector encourage profit-maximising behaviours by actors such as doctors, hospitals, as well as insurance and pharmaceutical companies. Moreover, oligopolistic market structures and the presence of intellectual property patents in the medical sector (Corlet Walker et al., 2021) enable firms to extract economic rents (Standing, 2016; Stiglitz, 2016; Stratford, 2020; United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2017). The privatised character of parts of the welfare state also facilitates rent-seeking, as Corlet Walker & Jackson (2021) demonstrate for the adult social care sector in the United Kingdom, where investors engage in predatory financial practices (such as debt-leveraged buyouts) to generate high financial returns. The pursuit of higher profits, returns on investment, and rents not only results in increasing health care expenses but also in suboptimal social outcomes in terms of the quality of health care provision (Corlet Walker et al., 2021).

2.3 The revenue dilemma

²⁰ Stratford (2020, p. 2) defines rent as an economic reward with two characteristics: "(1) it is sustained through control of assets that cannot be quickly and widely replicated, and (2) it exceeds proportionate compensation for the labour of the recipient". Rent-seeking is thus the use of resources and time with the aim to extract rents.

The revenue side has – in contrast to the expenditure side – been widely overlooked in the literature on welfare state growth dependence²¹. This is peculiar insofar as dynamics that ostensibly erode the revenue-generating capacities for the welfare state give rise to similar fiscal imbalances as those that drive expenditures, at least in terms of a simplified accounting perspective. In what follows, I will try to give a preliminary discussion of two relevant drivers of the *revenue dilemma* that have been insinuated in the literature.

The first of these phenomena brings us back to the issue of demographic change and the projected rise of old-age dependency ratios. As Petschow et al. (2018a) rightly assert in their growth dependence analysis of the German social security system, demographic change brings about not only issues of increased demand for welfare state services but may also reduce the (relative) size of the workforce and thus the underlying tax base²². The ostensible decline of the working-age population in the future may thus put substantial pressures on the funding side of the welfare state (Rouzet et al., 2019), particularly because governments’ revenues in the EU-27 and the OECD rely heavily on labour taxes and social contributions (European Commission & Directorate-General for Taxation and Customs Union, 2022b; OECD, 2021).

A second dynamic contributing to the revenue dilemma entails the subversion of existing tax systems. As insinuated by Corlet Walker & Jackson (2021, p. 13f.), rent-seeking may play a pivotal role here: “Enabling the wealthy to continue to accumulate wealth (e.g. through tax cuts and deregulation) stands in contrast to the role of government in supporting those in need by providing a well-functioning social safety net (e.g. through adequately funding welfare services)”. In that regard, rent-seeking entails deliberate efforts “to co-opt legislation and other acts of governance” (Halliday & O’Flynn, 2018, p. 463) with the aim of preserving or increasing the wealth of a certain actor, most often to the detriment of the public good (Halliday & O’Flynn, 2018; Stiglitz, 2016). Here, private actors readily employ lobbyists to bring about favourable conditions in their personal interest (Halliday & O’Flynn, 2018; Hillman, 2013; United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2017). Rentier power is hence used to bring about a tax and subsidy system favourable for companies and the wealthy, that is a system with regressive elements and deliberate

²¹ Until now, the revenue side of the welfare state has mostly been discussed with respect to financing issues arising in the context of a post-growth transformation, i.e. the post-growth funding dilemma (see section 2.5).

²² It should be noted that long-term projections on demographic changes are of course subject to uncertainty and should thus be taken with a pinch of salt. First of all, future migration may increase the workforce and thus have an alleviating impact on rising old-age dependency ratios. Secondly, labour market developments are a crucial variable to consider, especially the labour market participation and inclusion of women, the elderly, and migrants (Rouzet et al., 2019). Certainly, these two issues will have an impact on demographic change in one way or the other and thus influence the governments’ capacities to raise revenue for welfare state provisioning.

loopholes built into it (Standing, 2016; Stiglitz, 2012). Moreover, rent-seeking may involve practices such as tax evasion and avoidance²³ (Standing, 2016; United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2017). All these forms of rent-seeking thus undermine the revenue generating capacities of governments either via the regressive restructuring of the tax system or through its (oftentimes even fraudulent) subversion, thus contributing to the revenue dilemma of the welfare state. It is thus unsurprising, that rent-seeking and the related rise of rentier capitalism have been repeatedly identified as a major source of rising inequalities (Mazzucato, 2018; Standing, 2016; Stiglitz, 2012, 2016; Stratford, 2020; United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2017).

2.4 The automatic stabiliser dilemma

A third type of welfare state growth dependence arises from the operating principles of the so-called automatic stabilisers²⁴ in the field of non-discretionary fiscal policies (Bailey, 2015; Büchs, 2021). These automatic stabilisers have significant fiscal implications, as they affect both revenues and expenditures countercyclically (Mitchell et al., 2019). In that regard, economic downturns simultaneously generate pressures on the funding of welfare state programmes due to reduced economic activity on the one hand, while resulting in increased welfare spending (e.g. for unemployment benefits and income support schemes) on the other (Büchs, 2021). The Great Recession following the financial crisis of 2007/08 is a case in point. As countries entered into economic decline, tax revenues from consumption, employment and corporate profit fell harshly hence leading to considerable reductions in state revenue, while soaring unemployment (among other socioeconomic impacts) resulted in substantial increases in welfare state expenditures (Farnsworth & Irving, 2018; Gough, 2011).

Naturally, the operation of these automatic stabilisers results in fiscal deficits during a recession, thus worsening the budgetary positions of countries in the short-term. Their operation, however, also helps to stabilise aggregate demand and production, hence providing stimuli for economic recovery and hereby laying the foundation for economic growth²⁵ and corollary budgetary

²³ The Tax Justice Network (2021) estimates that – in 2021 – revenue losses due to cross-border tax abuse amounted to US\$483 billion worldwide.

²⁴ The notion of automatic stabilisers is grounded in Keynesian economic thought and the related proposition that it is the state's responsibility to smooth fluctuations in the business cycle, with the aim to facilitate economic growth and full employment (Morgan, 2013).

²⁵ In that regard, welfare states also act as growth drivers (Büchs, 2021; Büchs & Koch, 2019) and facilitators of capital accumulation (Gough, 1979; O'Connor, 2002; Offe, 1984a). Interestingly, welfare states – in their constitution as automatic stabilisers – essentially carry within them the potential remedy for their growth dependence.

surpluses to offset the debt accumulated in the future (Bailey, 2015). The countercyclical nature of welfare state funding and expenditure during economic downturns thus gives rise to what I call the *automatic stabiliser dilemma*. This type of growth dependence can be understood as an epiphenomenal, however, defining feature of welfare states, originating from their basic operating principles in a capitalist, growth-based economic system subject to business cycles²⁶.

2.5 The post-growth funding dilemma

Let us now turn to the fourth and last type of welfare state growth dependence, which shall be the main subject of concern within this master's thesis: the *post-growth funding dilemma*. As the name implies, this dilemma arises from the ways in which welfare state programmes are currently funded and the corollary difficulties this mode of funding may entail in the context of a post-growth society. In a degrowing economy²⁷, government tax revenues would inevitably decline compared to the status quo, as the extent of taxable economic activities decreases in conjunction, *ceteris paribus* resulting in fiscal pressures on welfare state funding (Bailey, 2015; Corlet Walker et al., 2021). Moreover, studies in the field of tax elasticity research suggests that, in times of economic downturns, tax revenues contract more sharply vis-à-vis the respective tax bases (Sancak et al., 2010). The fiscal issues emerging from the post-growth funding dilemma may thus be substantial if this finding also holds true in a post-growth scenario. The central question pertaining to the post-growth funding dilemma, as formulated by Cattaneo & Vansintjan (2016, p. 25, emphasis in original), may thus be: **“Without economic growth, how can we finance social services?”**

While this dilemma of funding welfare state expenditure in a non-growing economy has been repeatedly acknowledged within the discourses surrounding sustainable welfare and post-growth (Bailey, 2015; Büchs, 2021; Cattaneo & Vansintjan, 2016; Corlet Walker et al., 2021; Hausknost, 2020; Petschow et al., 2018a; Richters & Siemoneit, 2019; Seidl & Zahrnt, 2010b), it has not yet been investigated in sufficient detail. Oftentimes, the post-growth funding dilemma is primarily

²⁶ The automatic stabiliser dilemma raises intricate questions pertaining to the economic constitution of a post-growth society and the function of welfare states therein. Acknowledging that welfare states act as automatic stabilisers and hence as growth drivers is inherently problematic in the context of a post-growth transformation, as it conflicts with the ecological necessity of a degrowing economy that reduces its economic activities to sustainable levels. Therefore, a post-growth transformation would most probably also necessitate a recalibration of the welfare state aimed at alleviating its growth-driving characteristics, while preserving its socio-politically desirable functions. A close consideration of the automatic stabiliser dilemma also highlights more fundamental questions concerning a post-growth society, e.g. whether and to what extent a degrowing economy would still be subject to dynamics resembling contemporary business cycles. It is likely that a degrowing economy would substantially challenge the notion of business cycles altogether and might even put an end to the cyclical nature of economic processes as we know them.

²⁷ It should be noted that this argument would – at least to some extent – also apply to economies subject to secular stagnation.

addressed as an accounting issue of public finance, while not thoroughly considering *how* welfare states' expenditures are funded and *from which* tax bases these revenues are generated. These questions are, however, crucial, as the funding of the welfare state can take place in various manners, which might in turn give rise to particular manifestations of the post-growth funding dilemma.

As pointed out before, welfare state programmes can be financed via taxation and social contributions (Cichon et al., 2004; Manow, 2010; Morel & Palme, 2018; Obinger, 2021; Schmitt et al., 2020). Most importantly, (welfare) states' funding also considerably varies with respect to the relative importance of different tax bases such as labour, corporate profit, capital, property, land, and consumption (European Commission & Directorate-General for Taxation and Customs Union, 2022b; Morel & Palme, 2018; Obinger, 2021; OECD, 2021). In that regard, Büchs & Koch (2017) raise the question of whether some welfare regimes may be more or less growth dependent than others, given the varying combinations of these funding modes in conjunction with the particular benefits and services welfare states provide. Acknowledging that the tax sources and the underlying economic activities might themselves be growth dependent in varying ways (Corlet Walker et al., 2021), it becomes apparent that the post-growth funding dilemma may not only be a question of simple accounting but further raises interconnected issues pertaining to the growth dependence of the whole economic system and its constituting subsystems. It is thus crucial to disentangle the post-growth funding dilemma by scrutinising the ostensible growth dependencies of those socioeconomic areas which serve as the funding basis of welfare state provisioning. Such a holistic and disaggregated analysis of the post-growth funding dilemma – as also put forward by Corlet Walker et al. (2021) as a promising avenue for further research – is, however, currently missing within the literature.

With respect to this intimated research gap, there are, however, a few notable exceptions in the literature offering a more differentiated analysis of the post-growth funding dilemma. In that regard, the significance of employment as a source of revenue has been identified as a major cause of welfare states' growth dependence (Corlet Walker et al., 2021; Hoffmann & Paulsen, 2020; Petschow et al., 2018a; Richters & Siemoneit, 2019). In the EU-27, more than fifty percent of total tax revenues come from the taxation of labour, including social contributions (European Commission & Directorate-General for Taxation and Customs Union, 2022b). Hence, welfare states particularly rely on labour taxes and social contributions to fund their expenditures. Crucially, employment is in itself a growth dependent socioeconomic area, as the continuous rise

in labour productivity through technological change necessitates a corresponding expansion of economic activities in order to even maintain a certain employment level²⁸ (Hoffmann & Paulsen, 2020; Jackson & Victor, 2011; Richters & Siemoneit, 2019; Wiedmann et al., 2020). In other words, continuous economic growth is a prerequisite to avoid rising unemployment. Richters & Siemoneit (2019) argue that this phenomenon contributes to a political growth imperative, as politicians are compelled to pursue economic growth as a primary socio-political goal in order to avoid unemployment and the corollary fiscal pressures on public budgets, and welfare state systems in particular. They thus come to the conclusion that (welfare) states are themselves not growth dependent *stricto sensu*, as “keeping the revenues and costs of the (welfare) state in balance rather seems to depend on high employment” (Richters & Siemoneit, 2019, p. 133). Hoffmann & Paulsen (2020) reach a similar conclusion inferring that the welfare state is dependent on wage labour for generating revenues to fund systems of social security.

The case of employment highlights the central consideration that prompts the research focus of this master’s thesis. The post-growth funding dilemma cannot be thoroughly understood only in terms of a simple fiscal dependence of welfare states on economic growth. Rather, it is necessary to carefully consider the intricate growth dependencies within the capitalist economic system and how they affect the potentials to generate revenue from different tax bases. In that regard, the post-growth funding dilemma may not constitute a particular growth dependence of the welfare state in and of itself but rather arises epiphenomenally, as welfare state expenditure is funded via taxes and social contributions from socioeconomic areas which are themselves ostensibly growth dependent. In other words, the post-growth funding dilemma constitutes a *second-order* growth dependence. In that regard, the post-growth funding dilemma is distinct from the other three welfare state dilemmas, which are forms of first-order growth dependence²⁹.

The above considerations, in turn, raise questions of how and to which extent the welfare state’s reliance on tax bases other than labour may contribute to the post-growth funding dilemma. Are these tax bases similarly growth dependent as is the case for employment? And what does this imply for the post-growth funding dilemma of the welfare state? Moreover, are tax-based or contribution-based modes of financing welfare programmes more prone to issues emerging from the post-growth funding dilemma? And finally, what areas of welfare state provisioning might be most affected by the post-growth funding dilemma? These are some of the questions that I seek

²⁸ The argument is presented in more detail in chapter 5.2.1.

²⁹ Here, first-order growth dependence simply indicates that the dilemmas arise due to dynamics and phenomena *other* than growth dependence.

to address in the scope of this master's thesis. It is hence the purpose of this master's thesis to analyse how and to which extent the post-growth funding dilemma³⁰ constitutes the corollary of multidimensional growth dependencies within the current economic system.

3. The political economy of the post-growth funding dilemma

To gain a more pronounced understanding of the interconnected issues emerging from the post-growth funding dilemma of the welfare state, it seems expedient to investigate the role of welfare states within the political economy of welfare capitalism from a theoretical-historical perspective. In that regard, neo-Marxist theories of the state and historical institutionalism may provide illuminating insights. As we will see, the post-growth funding dilemma cannot be fully comprehended only in terms of a straightforward fiscal growth dependence, but rather constitutes an expression of inherently contradictory features of welfare capitalism.

3.1 The historical evolution of state imperatives

In the class-analytic approach to state theory (vom Hau, 2015), state transformations are often discussed in terms of functional state imperatives and their historical evolution. These state imperatives “can be defined as the functions that governmental structures have to carry out to ensure their own longevity and stability” (Dryzek et al., 2002, p. 662f.). The early modern state was characterised by three defining imperatives: maintaining domestic order, protecting the state against external threats and raising the revenue necessary to fulfil the two former functions (Dryzek et al., 2002; Hausknost, 2020; Skocpol, 2008). The emergence of capitalism and market economies was accompanied by fundamental transformations of the social relations and political institutions (Polanyi, 2001), leading to the successive emergence of two further imperatives: the imperative of economic growth or capital accumulation³¹ and the imperative of democratic legitimation (Dryzek et al., 2002; Hausknost, 2020).

To comprehend the evolution of state functions, two considerations must be taken into account. First, the addition of state imperatives stems from the endeavours of classes or social movements

³⁰ Henceforth, I will use the term ‘welfare state growth dependence’ to refer exclusively to the post-growth funding dilemma, unless otherwise indicated.

³¹ Even though analytically distinct phenomenon, economic growth and capital accumulation are of course closely interlinked, the former being the macroeconomic result of the latter (Andreucci & McDonough, 2015; Blauwhof, 2012; Pineault, 2018; Scarano, 2018; Wood, 2012).

to integrate their political interests into the logics of the state (Dryzek et al., 2002). Secondly, state imperatives follow a cumulative logic; thus, it is only possible for a new imperative to emerge if it can be reconciled with the existing configuration of state imperatives (Hausknost, 2020). The economic expansion brought about by capitalism promoted and facilitated both the generation of state revenue as well as the preservation of internal order in early capitalist societies. Thus, a fourth state imperative materialised, the imperative of economic growth or capital accumulation³² (Dryzek et al., 2002).

Soon, however, an organised working-class movement emerged, which jeopardised the political stability of the capitalist state. What thus materialised from the imperative of domestic order was a democratisation of the state and the establishment of the welfare state “to cushion the working class against the dislocations of capitalism” (Dryzek et al., 2002, p. 662). The welfare state³³ thus lies at the heart of the fifth state imperative, the imperative of democratic legitimation (Offe, 1984a). The genesis of the welfare state as an expression of the legitimation imperative was, however, only possible insofar as it could be reconciled with the accumulation imperative. In other words, the welfare state’s existence is predicated upon the fact that it not only serves the interests of the working class but also further enables and facilitates capital accumulation, primarily through the reproduction of the labour force³⁴ (Gough, 1979; O’Connor, 2002). In that regard, the welfare state and its policies are “supposed to be 'negatively subordinated' to the process of capitalist accumulation” (Keane, 1984, p. 14). Taken together, these five state imperatives constitute the core of contemporary democratic-capitalist states and hence public officials will always be compelled to act in accordance with them (Dryzek et al., 2002).

3.2 The contradictory double bind of the democratic-capitalist state

Despite the cumulative logic of state imperatives, the state may encounter disharmonious developments that give rise to internal contradictions (Hausknost, 2020). One of the most notable analyses of such internal contradictions pertains to the welfare state and has been undertaken by neo-Marxist scholar Claus Offe³⁵. In a nutshell, Offe’s (1982, p. 11, emphasis in original) main

³² In the Communist Manifesto, Marx and Engels (2017) put forward the well-known proposition that, in capitalism, the state works to advance the interests of the dominant capitalist class (Wetherly, 2005).

³³ Speaking in Polanyian terms, Quilley (2012, p. 206) interprets the emergence of the Keynesian welfare state as an expression of a “counter movement for societal protection”.

³⁴ Accordingly, Ian Gough (1979, p. 44f., emphasis in original) characterises the welfare state as “*the use of state power to modify the reproduction of labour power and to maintain the non-working population in capitalist societies*”.

³⁵ The richness and depth of Claus Offe’s critical state theory cannot be appreciated in detail here due to its sheer volume. My account of Offe’s contradictions of the welfare state must thus remain selective and partially superficial

thesis is that “while capitalism cannot coexist *with* the welfare state, neither can it exist *without* the welfare state. This is exactly the condition to which we refer when using the concept ‘contradiction’”. This contradiction arises due to the “precarious double function“ (Offe, 1984b, p. 55) of the state pertaining to the imperative of accumulation³⁶ and legitimation³⁷, a conflicting commitment which Lessenich (2009, p. 148f.) accurately refers to as the “double bind”³⁸ of the democratic-capitalist state. In that regard, Borchert & Lessenich (2016, p. 40, emphasis in original) contend that there exists a “functional antagonism [...] *between* the accumulation requirements of the capitalist economy and the legitimation demands of democratic politics”, which entails “an inherent potential for systemic conflict and disintegration”.

Essentially, the welfare state – as a pivotal vehicle for the legitimation of the capitalist state and its institutions – tends to structurally undermine capitalism’s capacity for commodification and accumulation, and thus the basis for the continued expansion of the economy³⁹. The late capitalist state thus finds itself with confronted with “crises of crisis management”, as Offe (1984b) succinctly contends. Picking up on arguments against the welfare state usually articulated by the political right, Offe (1982) argues that the welfare state impinges on capital accumulation in two ways: First of all, the funding of the welfare state is contingent upon taxation and regulation, which, however, disincentivise investment on the capital side and reduces the profitability of business. Secondly, the welfare state ostensibly disincentivises work – or at least reduces its productivity and extent – because welfare programmes (e.g. unemployment insurance) mitigate the exploitation of labour and enable workers to (temporarily) refuse unsatisfactory jobs and working conditions. Offe (1982, p. 9) contends that these conservative arguments indeed have some validity to them: “The reactionary political uses of this analysis are obvious, but it may well be that the truth of the analysis itself is greater than the desirability of its practical conclusions”.

within the scope of my argumentation. The interested reader may confer Borchert & Lessenich (2016) for a contemporary in-depth discussion of Offe’s ideas and contributions.

³⁶ The accumulation imperative as elaborated by Offe is conceptually based on Marx’s (1981) analysis of capital and its endless circulation, as indicated by the famous formula M-C-M’ (Borchert & Lessenich, 2016). In section 5.2.2., I elaborate on the general formula of capital circulation and further discuss its implications for welfare state growth dependence.

³⁷ According to Borchert & Lessenich (2016), Offe adopted the conception of these two contradictory state imperatives from James O’Connor (2002).

³⁸ The double bind has been described as a psychological phenomenon by Bateson et al. (1956) to theorise the development of schizophrenia. It refers to a situation in which a person is presented with conflicting demands or messages, whereby it is impossible to adequately react to both of them simultaneously. Most importantly, the person confronted with a double bind situation is neither able to resolve the dilemma nor opt-out of the situation.

³⁹ This, of course, is not to deny the significance of the welfare state in facilitating economic growth and capital accumulation (Gough, 1979; O’Connor, 2002; Offe, 1984a). Rather the dual nature of the welfare state as a both a facilitator and inhibitor of economic growth and capital accumulation, respectively, highlights its inherently contradictory character in capitalist societies.

Another substantial issue of late capitalism arises due to the decommodifying nature of the welfare state. Decommodification⁴⁰ – understood as the emancipation of social areas and individuals from the dominance of market relations – fundamentally opposes the capitalist logic of exchange and hence subverts the societal significance of capitalist structures (Offe, 1984b). Given that the welfare state impedes on capital accumulation through its disincentivising features and its decommodifying function⁴¹, Offe contends that these subversive tendencies of the welfare state substantially threaten its own reproduction: “While being designed to be a cure to some ills of capitalist accumulation, the nature of the illness is such that it may force the patient to refrain from using the cure” (Offe, 1982, p. 9).

Essentially, the welfare state is itself fiscally dependent on the financial prosperity and wealth originating from the economic sphere, as it extracts its revenues from the capitalist process of surplus-value creation⁴² (Offe, 1984b). The fundamental contradiction of the late capitalist state thus emerges from the fact, that “legitimation is expensive and lives on the fruits of accumulation, while accumulation is contested and needs the conditioning of legitimation” (Borchert & Lessenich, 2016). A likely materialisation of this contradiction is what James O’Connor⁴³ (2002) refers to as “the fiscal crisis of the state”. Such a fiscal crisis⁴⁴, O’Connor (2002, p. 221) argues, “is the inevitable consequence of the structural gap between state expenditures and revenues”. In short, the welfare state’s simultaneous dependence and subversion of the capitalist process of surplus-value production may give rise to intricate fiscal predicaments, as it undermines both the imperative of accumulation and revenue and hence the financial means for its own legitimating function. In other words, the imperative of democratic legitimation carries within it the potential for a fiscal crisis of the welfare state (Farnsworth & Irving, 2018). The welfare state as an essential institutional arrangement securing political legitimation thus finds itself in an ambiguous symbiosis with the imperative of capital accumulation. The welfare state is both dependent on surplus-value

⁴⁰ Drawing on Offe’s writings, Gøsta Esping-Andersen (1985, 1990) then popularised the concept of decommodification in welfare state research.

⁴¹ Lacher (1999) argues that while the welfare state indeed implied a partial decommodification of labour, this development was accompanied by an intensification of commodification in other realms of society, as it facilitated the rise of mass production and consumer societies

⁴² As Prychitko (1990) notes, there are notable parallels between Offe’s arguments and Joseph Schumpeter’s (1918) analysis articulated in the article *The crisis of the tax state*. Schumpeter (1918, p. 20) writes: “In this world the state lives as an economic parasite. It can withdraw from the private economy only as much as is consistent with the continued existence of this individual interest in every particular socio-psychological situation. In other words, the tax state must not demand from the people so much that they lose financial interest in production or at any rate cease to use their best energies for it”.

⁴³ Gough (1996) offers both an overview and critical assessment of O’Connor’s contribution.

⁴⁴ According to O’Connor, this structural gap arises due to the simultaneous socialisation of costs through the state and the private appropriation of social surpluses.

production and the expansion of the economy to fund its expenditure, while simultaneously inhibiting capital accumulation via taxation and regulation.

3.3 The post-growth funding dilemma as a latent contradiction of welfare capitalism

To understand why the fundamental contradiction between accumulation and democratic legitimation has not (yet) materialised into a destructive spiral of systemic disintegration, it is expedient to consider Offe's conceptualisation of the term 'contradiction'. Offe (1984c) emphasises that contradictions do not imply an immediate crisis or breakdown of the capitalist mode of production. Rather the self-destructive crisis tendencies of capitalist contradictions "can well be controlled and kept latent through various adaptive mechanisms of the system, at least temporarily" (Offe, 1984c, p. 133). Here, economic growth represents a feasible means to service the conflicting requirements of accumulation and legitimation simultaneously, thus keeping the contradiction of the welfare state latent. Until now, the contradictions arising from the state's double bind have been (more or less) well manageable in the presence of sufficiently high rates of economic growth "by facilitating reasonable levels of profit, wages, employment and other public goods simultaneously" (Ferguson, 2018, p. 76).

The contradiction of the welfare state and its socioeconomic implications gain an additional layer of significance when considering yet another contradictory characteristic of the capitalist economic system, namely the ecological contradiction of capitalism. In neo-Marxist literature, this ecological contradiction of capitalism has been termed "the second contradiction of capitalism" (O'Connor, 1988, 1991) and "the absolute general law of environmental degradation under capitalism" (Foster, 1992), respectively. No matter the name one may assign to it, the ecological contradiction of capitalism suggests that capitalism tends to structurally undermine the natural conditions of production essential to capitalism's reproduction (O'Connor, 1998). In essence, capital is locked in a "treadmill of production" (Gould et al., 2008; Schnaiberg, 1980) that must at one point enter into conflict with the biophysical boundaries of the Earth system due to the continuously increasing scale of productive activities (Foster, 2011b). It is thus with a view to this ecological contradiction that economic growth and the continuous need for capital accumulation present themselves as inherently irreconcilable with sustainability requirements. Therefore, a transformation toward a post-growth – and indeed post-capitalist – economy is an ecological imperative.

In a post-growth economy, however, the contradictions between capitalism and democracy can no longer be mediated through politics of growth. A social-ecological transformation of the socioeconomic system thus entails potentials for multidimensional social and economic crises. According to Habermas (1988, p. 2), “crises arise when the structure of a social system allows fewer possibilities for problem solving than are necessary to the continued existence of the system”. Certainly, the preclusion of further economic growth as a mode of problem solving would thus threaten the functionality of the capitalist economic system and the democratic state: “It is an understatement to say that such ‘post-growth by design’ challenges most of the tenets of welfare capitalism” (Gough, 2021, p. 913). Since a sustainability imperative cannot be integrated into the current configuration of state imperatives without major contradictions⁴⁵ (Hausknot, 2020), the central challenge is to overcome the intricate interdependencies between accumulation and legitimation, between capitalism and democracy, that currently lock societies in an escalatory spiral of unsustainability and ultimately social-ecological crises. For a social-ecological transformation to be realised, it is hence imperative to transcend the imperative of accumulation and growth while preserving the institutions that constitute the fabric of democratic societies.

Coming back to the issue of welfare state growth dependence, the neo-Marxist account of inherently conflictual state imperatives clearly highlights that the post-growth funding dilemma does not solely represent an issue arising from the ecological necessity of a profound societal transformation. Rather, the post-growth funding dilemma must be understood as the corollary of the capitalist democratic state’s double bind. In that regard, the post-growth funding dilemma is essentially a structural, however, currently latent contradiction of welfare capitalism. It is only with a view to a post-growth economy that the antagonisms between capitalism and democracy manifest into an ostensibly unmanageable fiscal crisis, the post-growth funding dilemma of the welfare state.

A post-growth transformation thus entails intricate questions for the future of the welfare state and the democratic foundations of society in general: Which structural features within the political economy of welfare capitalism give rise to the fiscal growth dependence of democratic legitimation in the first place? How may we avoid a fiscal crisis of the welfare state in a degrowing economic system? And even more substantially: Is it even possible to transcend the imperative of growth and accumulation while preserving the welfare state as an essential element of democratic

⁴⁵ Hausknot (2020) also contends that a sustainability imperative is a logical impossibility, since the legitimation imperative must by definition subsume any further claims voiced by a social movement or class. In other words, sustainability can only be demanded within the realm of the democratic legitimation imperative.

legitimation? These are some of the fundamental questions that I seek to address in my analysis of the post-growth funding dilemma of the welfare state.

4. The Austrian welfare state

4.1 Substantiating the choice of the Austrian welfare state as a case study

Let us commence this chapter with some methodological considerations. Essentially, I seek to investigate the post-growth funding dilemma using a case study approach (Yin, 2018). According to Gerring (2017, p. 28), a case study can be defined as “an intensive study of a single case or a small number of cases which draws on observational data and promises to shed light on a larger population of cases”. For my analysis, I draw on a single case, namely the Austrian welfare state and in particular its modes of provisioning and funding to shed light on the ways in which growth dependencies manifest in terms of the post-growth funding dilemma of the welfare state.

My case study choice is based on a purposeful sampling technique well-suited for an in-depth analysis of an information-rich case with the aim of answering the research question investigated (Patton, 2015). More specifically, I employ what Patton (2015) terms a single significant case sampling strategy, which aims at the identification of a single case able to provide comprehensive insights due its specific characteristics. I thus select the Austrian welfare state as my object of analysis based on the following considerations.

First of all, the Austrian welfare state may be referred to as an established welfare state (Arts & Gelissen, 2010) with well-developed public welfare programmes and an extensive social safety net. In international comparative perspective, the Austrian welfare state exhibits a distinctly above-average level of social expenditures coupled with a favourable performance in terms of socioeconomic outcomes (Obinger, 2015). In that regard, the imperative of democratic legitimation is ostensibly well-established, meaning that the contradictory nature of welfare capitalism in terms of the post-growth funding dilemma is well accessible for analytic inquiry.

Secondly, the Austrian welfare state is a well-suited object of research, as it represents a so-called typical case, i.e. “a case chosen by virtue of representing features that are common within a larger population” (Gerring, 2017, p. 56). Specifically, welfare programmes in Austria are organised in terms of the various modes of funding representative of welfare state financing in general, that is

financing via social contributions, taxes, and a combination thereof. Moreover, the Austrian welfare state also relies on different tax bases to fund its expenditures. Despite the funding-related idiosyncrasies present in different welfare states, the fundamental mechanisms underlying the post-growth funding dilemma discussed here seem to be rather constitutive of welfare capitalism in general. Therefore, the basic conclusions drawn from my analysis of growth dependencies may be tentatively generalisable and hence extended to other welfare states when considering their respective composition of funding.

Beside these methodological considerations, the choice of the Austrian welfare state as my case study is further prompted by the fact that Austria substantially transgresses its national per capita biophysical boundaries, while performing particularly well in terms of social indicators (Fanning et al., 2022). The social-ecological challenge for Austria – as for other high-income countries of the Global North – is hence to decouple its social performance from unsustainable levels of socio-metabolic throughput. As elaborated in the introduction, this requires a post-growth transformation of the economy and thus an overcoming of structural growth dependencies. In that regard, the intricate issues manifest in the post-growth funding dilemma are of utmost significance for Austria's ambitions to expedite a social-ecological transformation.

4.2 What is a welfare state? A clarification of terms

Before looking into the constitution of the Austrian welfare state in more detail, it is instructive to elaborate on some terminological clarifications regarding the welfare state. The first and most basic question in that regard must be: What is a welfare state? According to Kuhlmann (2018), giving a definite definition of what constitutes a welfare state is quite difficult – if not impossible – for a number of reasons. First of all, there exists considerable empirical diversity within welfare states around the world (Béland, Morgan, et al., 2021; Greve, 2019) as well as within Europe (Schubert et al., 2016). Secondly, the concept of the welfare state greatly varies in meaning over both time and geographical context (Petersen & Petersen, 2013). Thirdly, the concept of the welfare state itself encompasses two highly contested terms, 'welfare' and 'state', thereby further complicating the formulation of a definition (Kuhlmann, 2018). Given these considerations, it is crucial to clarify as concisely as possible what the term 'welfare state' refers to as an analytical concept within the scope of this analysis.

In his seminal contribution *The three worlds of welfare capitalism*, Esping-Andersen (1990) delineates a narrow and a broad definition of the welfare state⁴⁶. The broad definition explicitly links the welfare state to the sphere of the political economy, whereby “issues of employment, wages, and overall macro-economic steering are considered integral components in the welfare-state complex” (Esping-Andersen, 1990, p. 2). The narrow definition on the other hand refers to the more tangible modes and programmes of welfare state provisioning, i.e. “the traditional terrain of social amelioration” (Esping-Andersen, 1990, p. 1).

For the purpose of this analysis, both definitions are of central relevance. Acknowledging the growth dependence of the welfare state in the first place, requires a recognition of the political economy of welfare capitalism that is essentially centred around accumulation and expansion on the one hand and democratic legitimation on the other. In this sense, the broad definition of the welfare state is what implicitly constitutes the ontological basis of my analysis. The narrow definition, on the other hand, delineates the welfare state as the particular research object of this analysis. Here, Richard Titmuss’ (1959) notion of a social division of welfare is expedient.

Titmuss argues that the welfare state entails three modes of intervention: occupational welfare, fiscal welfare, and social welfare⁴⁷. Occupational welfare denotes such benefits which are offered by employers for their employees, particularly non-statutory occupational pensions as well as fringe benefits such as company cars or canteens (Farnsworth, 2018). Fiscal welfare, on the other hand, comprises benefits provided through the system of taxation, e.g. tax allowances or exemptions (Sinfield, 2018). Contrastingly, social welfare refers⁴⁸ to “formal publicly financed and provided social programmes” (Morel & Palme, 2018, p. 468) and thus entails the “direct public provision of cash and in-kind benefits to individuals and families, free or at below market cost” (Abramovitz, 2001, p. 299). Given the above delineations, my analysis of the post-growth funding dilemma will be primarily concerned with the social variant of welfare state provisioning⁴⁹.

4.3 The Austrian welfare state in welfare regime perspective

⁴⁶ See also Garland (2014) and Kuhlmann (2018) for similar notions.

⁴⁷ Titmuss’ typology may be broadened to take into account self-provisioning, legal welfare – i.e. welfare provided by the legal system (Adema & Whiteford, 2021) –, as well as the welfare provided pervasively by the unpaid labour of women in the context of the sexual division of labour (Rose, 1981).

⁴⁸ Sinfield (1978) refers to this sphere of the welfare state as *public* welfare and the *public* system of welfare, respectively, to accurately highlight their public provisioning character.

⁴⁹ As we will see in section 4.4, data on Austria’s social protection expenditures also covers forms of fiscal and occupational welfare. These instances will hence also be considered in the analysis of the Austrian welfare state.

This section provides a short overview of the characteristics of the Austrian welfare state by drawing on welfare state regime typologies. Here, the analytical point of departure is – unsurprisingly – Gøsta Esping-Andersen’s (1990) seminal contribution *The three worlds of welfare capitalism*. Building on Esping-Andersen’s account of ideal-typical welfare state regimes, the Austrian welfare state can be categorised as a conservative-corporatist and continental welfare state, respectively (Esping-Andersen, 1990; Leichsenring, 2017; Obinger, 2015; Obinger & Tálós, 2010; Österle & Heitzmann, 2016, 2019; Tálós, 2015; Tálós & Obinger, 2020; Unger & Heitzmann, 2003). Beyond Esping-Andersen’s well-known typology, the Austrian welfare state can also be classified as a Bismarckian welfare state⁵⁰ (Obinger & Tálós, 2010).

In its constitution as a conservative-corporatist regime, the Austrian welfare state is characterised by the centrality of social security systems covering the spheres of old-age, health care and sickness, unemployment, as well as workplace accidents. Here, welfare benefits and entitlements primarily depend on the contributions made and therefore on individuals’ employment and the respective level of income (Arts & Gelissen, 2002; Clegg, 2018; Kersbergen, 2018). Social rights are hence very much connected to occupational status and social class (Esping-Andersen, 1990). The centrality of social security as an organising principle also implies that the bulk of welfare state provisioning is financed via social contributions, with a more limited role for tax-based funding (Bonoli, 1997; Manow, 2010). Universal programmes – prevalent in the domains of family policy and long-term care – as well as poverty relief in terms of social assistance are in turn only of secondary significance in the Austrian welfare state (Heitzmann & Österle, 2008; Österle & Heitzmann, 2016, 2019). Moreover, the corporatist character of the Austrian welfare state indicates the strong role and political influence of social partners regarding the development and structure of welfare state provisioning (Österle & Heitzmann, 2019; Paster, 2014; Rathgeb, 2017; Tálós & Obinger, 2020).

From a gender perspective (Sainsbury, 1999), the Austrian welfare state can be characterised as a male breadwinner regime (Österle & Heitzmann, 2016, 2019). Based on the ideology of male privilege and a sexual division of labour, women – in their role as wives – are primarily subjugated to providing care and performing unpaid work at home (Sainsbury, 1999), while their participation on the labour market is discouraged through the gendered design of the welfare system (Arts & Gelissen, 2002; Kersbergen, 2018). Due to these characteristics, the Austrian welfare state

⁵⁰ The conservative-corporatist regime is very much rooted in Otto von Bismarck’s conception of welfare state provisioning based on a social insurance system (Esping-Andersen, 1990).

facilitates the reproduction of status differentials along the lines of class, occupational status and gender (Esping-Andersen, 1990; Kersbergen, 2018).

4.4 The social expenditures of the Austrian welfare state

Having situated the Austrian welfare state in the context of comparative welfare state research, let us now take a brief look into the extent of social protection expenditure and the spheres of welfare state provisioning in Austria. For this purpose, I employ data from Statistik Austria, which calculates social protection expenditure based on the guidelines and definitions put forward by Eurostat in the European System of Integrated Social Protection Statistics (ESSPROS). According to ESSPROS, social protection⁵¹ “encompasses all interventions from public or private bodies intended to relieve households and individuals of the burden of a defined set of risks or needs, provided that there is neither a simultaneous reciprocal nor an individual arrangement involved” (Eurostat, 2008, p. 9).

In Austria, social protection expenditure amounted to €129 billion⁵² in 2020, that is circa 14,200€ of social protection expenditure per inhabitant. In relative terms, Austria’s social protection expenditure amounted to 34.1 % of its gross domestic product (GDP)⁵³. Looking at the development of social protection expenditure⁵⁴ depicted in figure 1, Austria’s social expenditure-to-GDP ratio has been slowly but steadily rising since 1990 (26.1 %). After an initial expansionary phase until 1995 (28.9 %), Austria’s social expenditure-to-GDP ratio decreased in the following years, reaching a low in 2007 (27 %). With the onset of the global financial crisis and the subsequent economic downturn, social protection expenditures rose once again and stabilised close to the 30 % mark. Starting in 2020, the COVID-19 crisis yet again resulted in a notable rise of Austria’s social expenditure-to-GDP ratio, largely driven by the simultaneous decline of economic output and the increasing demand for welfare state provisioning.

⁵¹ Note that this definition of social protection is not perfectly congruent with the notion of social welfare elaborated in section 4.2. Social protection expenditures for Austria also includes two instances of occupational welfare – namely voluntary occupational pension schemes (*Betriebliche Pensionsvorsorge*) and the statutory payment of wages by employers in the event of illness (*Arbeitgeberlohnfortzahlung bei Krankheit*) – as well as elements of fiscal welfare in the form of various tax allowances.

⁵² This figure not only includes direct expenditures for the provisioning of social benefits but also comprises the transfer of social contribution payments from one social protection scheme to another as well as other expenses such as administrative costs and interest payments.

⁵³ For a comparative discussion of OECD countries’ social expenditures see Obinger (2021) .

⁵⁴ A comprehensive discussion of welfare state developments as well as reforms in Austria is beyond the scope of this thesis and can be found elsewhere (Österle & Heitzmann, 2016, 2019; Tálos & Obinger, 2020). The interested reader may also confer Obinger (2015) and Österle & Heitzmann (2019) for an analysis and discussion of policy outputs and performance of the Austrian welfare state.

Figure 1: Social protection expenditure of the Austrian welfare state, 1990-2020

Note: Own calculations. Social protection expenditure per inhabitant has been adjusted for inflation based on Austria's consumer price index (CPI), base year 2020. Data sources: (Statistik Austria, 2021, 2022a, 2022b)

Let us now take a more disaggregated look at Austria's social expenditure. According to the ESSPROS manual (Eurostat, 2008), social protection comprises provisioning in the following areas: sickness and health care, disability, old-age, survivors, family and children, unemployment, housing, and lastly social exclusion not elsewhere classified. As is notable in figure 2, social expenditures in the two domains of old-age and sickness and health care are the largest areas of provisioning in the Austrian welfare state, amounting to 41.7 and 23.5 % of total social protection expenditure in 2020, respectively. Old-age and health care benefits thus make up almost two thirds of Austrian social protection expenditure. Social protection expenditure in the other provisioning areas is rather low in comparison: 12.3 % of total expenditure is used for unemployment-related benefits, 9.8 % for family and children programmes, 5.9 % for disability, 5 % for survivors, and 1.8 % for housing and social exclusion⁵⁵. The 2020 numbers do have to be taken with a pinch of salt, however, given the extraordinary impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on social policy in Austria. In particular, the exceptionally sharp rise of spending in the sphere of unemployment has

⁵⁵ In the data provided by Statistik Austria, these two domains are grouped together, even though they represent distinct categories according to the ESSPROS manual.

resulted in a relative decline of the shares in the other areas, thus potentially obscuring the fact that spending in all areas has nonetheless increased in absolute terms vis-à-vis the year 2019.

Figure 2: Social protection expenditure of the Austrian welfare state by function in % of total social protection expenditure, 1990-2020

Note: Own calculations. Data source: Statistik Austria (2021)

Let us now take a closer look at Austria’s social protection expenditures over time, focusing on the pre-COVID-19 time period up to 2019. As we can see, the relative shares of spending in the sphere of old-age and unemployment have markedly increased up to 2019. Notable increases are also discernible in the provisioning area of sickness and health care as well as in the sphere of housing and social exclusion. In the other areas, spendings as a share of total social protection expenditures have decreased over time, most notably in the domain of survivors. While figure 2 helps to illuminate the changing composition as well as relative significance of social protection provisioning over time, it does not necessarily reflect the concrete development of social protection expenditures in the different areas accurately. Hence, it further seems expedient to consider the development of social protection expenditure as a share of Austria’s GDP⁵⁶. Here, a rise of relative expenditure levels can be observed for the domains of old-age, sickness and health care, unemployment, family and children, as well as housing and social exclusion. In the case of

⁵⁶ A complimentary figure can be found in section 9.3 of the appendix.

disability- and survivors-related benefits, expenditures as a share of Austria's GDP have decreased since 1990, this decline being especially pronounced in the latter case.

5 Welfare state funding in the light of structural growth dependencies

While the expenditure side has received ample attention in welfare state research, the funding of welfare state provisioning and the underlying modes of revenue generation remain an under-researched subject matter (Manow, 2010; Morel & Palme, 2018; Obinger, 2021; Prasad & Deng, 2009; Schmitt et al., 2020). Unduly so, however, as is also signified by growing contemporary interest in the field of fiscal sociology (Martin et al., 2009; Martin & Prasad, 2014; Mumford, 2019). As Joseph Schumpeter (1918, p. 7) famously wrote in his essay *The crisis of the tax state*⁵⁷:

“The spirit of a people, its cultural level, its social structure, the deeds its policy may prepare – all this and more is written in its fiscal history, stripped of all phrases. He who knows how to listen to its message here discerns the thunder of world history more clearly than anywhere else”.

Indeed, the realm of public finance and taxation offers a unique perspective on the development and constitution of modern capitalist societies, of which the welfare state forms an integral part. The analysis of welfare state funding is thus politically and academically topical for a number of reasons.

First of all, the way in which welfare states are financed entails substantial (re-)distributive impacts in its own respect. Most importantly, direct taxes are usually more progressive than indirect taxes (e.g. taxes on consumption⁵⁸) and social contributions. With respect to social contribution schemes, this is due to the fact that these systems have ceilings placed on the extent of financial contributions while not entailing any forms of tax allowance. Social contribution-based financing of welfare state programmes thus tends to benefit individuals at the upper end of the income distribution, while implying a relatively high tax burden for individuals with low incomes⁵⁹ (Morel & Palme, 2018; Schmitt et al., 2020). With respect to the distributional aspects of welfare state funding in general, it is moreover noteworthy that the progressivity of the tax system is inversely

⁵⁷ The interested reader may confer Musgrave (1992) for a critical appreciation of Schumpeter's contribution.

⁵⁸ Consumption taxes of course regressive in nature, as individuals with low incomes spent a relatively large share of their income engaging in consumptive activities (Joumard et al., 2013; Morel & Palme, 2018; Prasad & Deng, 2009).

⁵⁹ Morel & Palme (2018) emphasise, however, that the regressive aspects present in the funding structure of social insurance systems are outweighed by the redistributive impacts of the programmes themselves, as social risks – such as unemployment or sickness – burden individuals at the bottom of the income distribution more heavily.

correlated with the size of the welfare state. In other words, well-developed welfare states tend to be funded through less progressive tax systems, as they rely on revenues from regressive taxes (e.g. consumption taxes) to finance social protection⁶⁰ (Prasad & Deng, 2009).

Secondly, the welfare state and its funding modes are politically highly contested issues. As the size of the welfare state is strongly correlated with the size of the tax state, well-developed welfare provisioning implies an extensive extraction of financial resources from society on a mandatory basis (Obinger, 2021). In that regard, welfare state funding impacts on individuals' willingness to pay and, in turn, affects the political legitimacy of welfare state institutions (Morel & Palme, 2018; Schmitt et al., 2020). Here, Manow (2010) argues that financing via social contribution systems tends to be associated with a higher degree of political legitimacy than tax financing, as social contributions are earmarked in the sense that they are directly connected to welfare entitlements and thus concrete benefits, hence increasing individuals' willingness to contribute. Moreover, welfare states with an emphasis on social contribution systems tend to be historically more stable and less susceptible to retrenchment than primarily tax-financed systems. This is because the latter are funded from the general government budget, which makes social protection all the more politically contested in times of financial constraints. Tax-financed welfare provisioning, however, entails the advantage of increased flexibility, giving governments more freedom in enacting social protection policies (Morel & Palme, 2018).

Thirdly, the funding modalities of welfare provisioning systems affect macroeconomic processes and outcomes, as social contribution systems and the imposition of taxes impact on wage costs and alter economic incentive structures. In that regard, the financing of the welfare state entails substantial implications for employment, competitiveness, and economic growth⁶¹. Welfare state funding thus entails potential socioeconomic trade-offs which require balancing through processes of political deliberation (Morel & Palme, 2018; Schmitt et al., 2020). Moreover, the way in which the welfare state is funded affects its countercyclical operation as an automatic stabiliser, which in turn has important implications for general economic performance and government finances throughout the business cycle (Mitchell et al., 2019).

⁶⁰ Drawing on work by Wilensky (2002), Prasad & Deng (2009) hypothesise that this inverse correlation may be explained by the fact that the reliance on regressive taxes can help to avoid high tax burdens on capital. The corollary form of redistribution through the welfare state thus occurs primarily *within* classes, which may help to secure the wealthy classes' support for the welfare state.

⁶¹ Recall the ambivalent nature of welfare states as both a facilitator and inhibitor of capital accumulation and economic growth insinuated in section 3.

Lastly, the modes of welfare state financing are of pivotal significance with respect to an integrated analysis of welfare states' growth dependence in general and the post-growth funding dilemma in particular. Therefore, let us now turn to an examination of the composition of Austrian welfare state funding to illuminate the relative importance of different tax bases for revenue generation.

5.1 The funding of the Austrian welfare state

In section 2.5, it was argued that the post-growth funding dilemma arises due to ostensible growth dependencies of those socioeconomic areas, which act as revenue sources for the funding of the welfare state. In other words, the tax bases relevant for welfare state funding may themselves be growth dependent. In that regard, it is necessary to delineate the funding of the Austrian welfare state with a view to the relative importance of different tax bases⁶². For the purpose of my analysis, I will distinguish between four different tax bases, namely labour, capital, land – i.e. the three classical factors of production (Ryan-Collins et al., 2017) –, as well as consumption. These four tax bases have been chosen as the units of my analysis, as they seem to be well suited for an investigation of growth dependencies due to their distinct characteristics and functions in the economic process (see section 5.2).

5.1.1 The tax base composition of welfare state funding in Austria

For the purpose of investigating the composition of welfare state funding in Austria, I combine data by Statistik Austria (2021) on the funding of the Austrian welfare state and National Tax List data for Austria provided by Eurostat (2022). The latter comprises not only a comprehensive overview of all taxes and social contributions in Austria, but also an allocation to different tax base categories⁶³. The methodological steps taken to combine the two data sets can be found in section 9.1 of the appendix.

⁶² Given the possibly misleading terminology pertaining to the word 'tax base', it should be noted that social contributions are also allocated to a tax base, despite them not being taxes in the narrow sense of the word.

⁶³ The relevant methodological notes on the primary tax base categories (i.e. labour, capital, and consumption) can be found in annex B of the publication *Taxation trends in the European Union: data for the EU Member States, Iceland, Norway: 2022 edition* (European Commission & Directorate-General for Taxation and Customs Union, 2022b). Moreover, it must be noted that a minor amendment of the tax base allocation has been undertaken to include the tax base category 'land'. In the primary tax base categories of Eurostat, taxes on land are included in the capital tax category. Due to its particular characteristics as a factor of production, land is, however, inherently dissimilar to capital (Gaffney, 1994; Ryan-Collins et al., 2017) and should be considered a tax base on its own (Mirrlees & Adam, 2011). I thus include land as an additional tax base category, which comprises the three land taxes discussed in the subsequent section. The complete tax base allocation of taxes and social contributions in Austria can be found in section 9.2 of the appendix.

Let us now examine the tax base composition of Austria’s welfare state funding depicted in figure 3. As is clearly apparent, the bulk of welfare state receipts stems from the factor labour. In 2020, more than two thirds of welfare state expenditures were financed by taxes and social contributions on labour. Conversely, the share of revenues from consumption and capital amounted to only 16.2 and 11.7 %, respectively. Land-related revenues provided an almost negligible amount of 0.3 % of total receipts to the financing of the Austrian welfare state. Lastly, other receipts⁶⁴ contributed 1.3 % to total welfare state receipts in 2020. Again, however, the results of 2020 should be taken with a pinch of salt considering the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic that year. As evident in figure 3, the year 2020 has seen notable changes in the tax base composition compared to 2019.

Figure 3: Tax base composition of Austria’s welfare state funding in % of total receipts, 1995-2020

Note: Own calculation. Data sources: Statistik Austria (2021) & Eurostat (2022)

Looking at the development of Austria’s welfare state funding composition, we can see that the share of revenues stemming from labour decreased markedly since 1995, while the share of both capital and consumption increased. This, however, does not necessarily imply that the funding contribution of labour has decreased over time. When examining the contributions of the tax bases

⁶⁴ Other receipts include property income and miscellaneous receipts.

as a share of GDP⁶⁵, it becomes apparent that the contributions of labour still increased slightly over time. The contributions of both capital and consumption, however, increased quite markedly relative to GDP, thus leading to the decreasing relative contribution of labour to Austrian welfare state receipts depicted in figure 3. Turning to taxes on land, we can see that their share of total welfare state receipts has been fluctuating between 0.2 and 0.3 % over time. Lastly, the share of revenues stemming from other receipts has grown considerably since 1995⁶⁶.

5.1.2 A (very) short overview of the Austrian tax system

Having scrutinised the composition of welfare state funding in Austria, a short overview of the most important taxes and social contributions in the respective socioeconomic areas is instructive⁶⁷. Let us start with the sphere of labour, which – as we have seen – is by far the most important contributor to welfare state funding among the four tax bases. As a conservative-corporatist welfare state, large parts of Austrian social protection are organised in systems of social security (Heitzmann & Österle, 2008; Österle & Heitzmann, 2019). This means that the factor labour bears the bulk of social security contributions⁶⁸ used for financing the pension system, health care, and unemployment benefits among other areas of social protection. The two most important labour taxes are the income tax (*Einkommenssteuer*) and the wage tax (*Lohnsteuer*)⁶⁹, both of which are progressive in nature.

Capital is subject to a relatively low level of taxation in Austria from a comparative European perspective (European Commission & Directorate-General for Taxation and Customs Union, 2022b). In Austria the most important capital taxes are the corporate income tax (*Körperschaftsteuer*) with a 25 % tax rate and the capital gains tax (*Kapitalertragssteuer*) with a tax rate of 25 and 27.5 % (depending on the specific type of capital income). Taxes on wealth and property only play a minor role in Austria's tax structure, as many relevant taxes – such as the wealth tax (*Vermögenssteuer*) as well as the inheritance and gift tax (*Erbschafts- und Schenkungssteuer*) – have been discontinued from the 1980s onwards (Schmidl & Schratzenstaller, 2011; Schratzenstaller, 2015).

⁶⁵ The relevant figure can be found in section 9.3 of the appendix.

⁶⁶ In the subsequent analysis, the category of 'other receipts' will not be considered.

⁶⁷ For a comprehensive overview of Austria's tax system, confer Köppl & Schratzenstaller (2015).

⁶⁸ Social contributions generally relate to the tax base of labour, irrespective of whether they are paid by employees or employers. The social contributions of the self-employed are, however, assigned to the tax base capital (European Commission & Directorate-General for Taxation and Customs Union, 2022b).

⁶⁹ It should be noted, however, that parts of these taxes are also allocated to the tax base capital, as they also comprise income from capital (European Commission & Directorate-General for Taxation and Customs Union, 2022b). The issue is further elaborated in section 9.2 of the appendix.

In the socioeconomic area of consumption, the most prominent tax in Austria is the value-added tax (*Umsatzsteuer*). While the standard value-added tax rate amounts to 20 %, some products and services have discounted rates of 13 and 10 %, respectively. In addition to the value-added tax, there exist several excise taxes, for instance on beer, tobacco, alcohol, and mineral oils. In European perspective, revenues from consumption taxes are relatively low in Austria (European Commission & Directorate-General for Taxation and Customs Union, 2022b)

Lastly, there exist three taxes on land in Austria. First, there is a tax on vacant plots (*Bodenwertabgabe*), i.e. a land value tax on undeveloped land suitable for construction purposes. Moreover, Austria has two types of real estate taxes. Real estate tax A (*Grundsteuer A*) is applied to agricultural land and forests, whereas real estate tax B (*Grundsteuer B*) covers the taxation of land in other uses⁷⁰. The almost negligible contribution of land to financing the Austrian welfare state certainly stems from the fact that revenues from land taxation generally rank among the lowest in the European Union (Claus et al., 2016).

5.2 The growth dependencies of the capitalist economic system

Now that we have illuminated the Austrian welfare state's funding composition, let us now turn to the analysis of growth dependencies within the capitalist economic system to properly delineate the intricate nature of the post-growth funding dilemma as a second-order growth dependence. Based on a focused literature review, this chapter seeks to explore whether distinct growth dependencies exist in the socioeconomic areas of labour, capital, land, and consumption⁷¹; and if so, what socioeconomic dynamics and phenomena may give rise to these growth dependencies. Again, the definition of growth dependence by Petschow et al. (2018a) is instructive and informs the subsequent analyses. Here, a social system or socioeconomic area can be defined as growth dependent if – under current conditions – its socio-politically desired functionality necessitates continuous growth of the economy. The question that hence underlies the reasoning in the following chapters is how a cessation of economic growth would affect the socioeconomic areas in question⁷². As will become apparent in this chapter, the current literature on growth

⁷⁰ Moreover, there exists a real estate transfer tax (*Gründerwerbssteuer*) which is levied on the acquisition of plots of land as well as buildings. This tax is, however, categorised as a capital tax here, as it does not tax land per se but rather the transfer of capital.

⁷¹ Crucially, the analyses are concerned with a growth dependence of the respective tax bases (e.g. labour) and *not* their valuation (e.g. wages).

⁷² It should be emphasised at this point, that growth dependence does not imply that there exists only a unidirectional relationship between economic growth and the socioeconomic area in question. Clearly, labour, capital, land, and consumption can themselves act as significant drivers of economic growth. Such growth-driving dynamics will,

dependencies has concerned itself almost exclusively with the sphere of labour, whereas the other three areas have received little to no attention. The attempted growth dependence analysis of capital, land, and consumption must thus be understood as explorative in nature, yielding hopefully insightful, however, non-definitive conclusions.

5.2.1 Employment and the productivity trap

The proposition that stable employment⁷³ is closely linked to the expansion of the economy has become a stylized fact in economics. The negative relation between a country's unemployment rate and the growth of the economy is commonly known as Okun's law (Ball, Leigh, & Loungani, 2013), named after the economist Arthur Okun (1963). Essentially, Okun's law implies that a lack of economic growth is associated with rising unemployment⁷⁴. In that regard, Okun's law seems to indicate a growth dependence of employment, as GDP growth is – at least under current conditions – necessary to keep employment levels stable. But how does this growth dependence come about? A plausible explanation may be found in the interrelated dynamics of capitalist competition, technological innovation, and the corollary trend of rising labour productivity (Antal & van den Bergh, 2013; Cahen-Fourot, 2022; Ferguson, 2018; Jackson & Victor, 2011; Richters & Siemoneit, 2017, 2019; Wiedmann et al., 2020).

To delineate the growth dependence of employment, it is first necessary to illuminate the circumstances under which firms operate in a capitalist market economy. Given the pressures emanating from (price) competition, firms can only survive in the market if they constantly reinvest (parts of) the surplus value appropriated in the production process (Blauwhof, 2012; Harvey, 2010; Sweezy, 1981; Wood, 2012). Marx (1981, p. 739) writes:

„The development of capitalist production makes it necessary constantly to increase the amount of capital laid out in a given industrial undertaking, and competition subordinates every individual capitalist to the immanent laws of capitalist production, as external and coercive laws. It compels him

however, only be of secondary interest for the present analytical purpose. For a comprehensive discussion of growth drivers see Petschow et al. (2018).

⁷³ I use the term 'employment' here instead of the more encompassing term 'labour', as the latter may also be understood as comprising forms of unpaid work. The present analysis is, however, only concerned with *paid* employment and *wage* labour, respectively. I nonetheless retain the use of the term labour when referring to the respective tax base.

⁷⁴ Empirically speaking, the strength of this relation is, however, subject to considerable heterogeneity. In other words, the responsiveness of employment to fluctuations in economic output differs notably between countries (Ball et al., 2019).

to keep extending his capital, so as to preserve it, and he can only extend it by means of progressive accumulation”.

This coercion to accumulate and reinvest capital stems from the necessity to continuously innovate in a competitive market characterised by the “perennial gale of creative destruction” (Schumpeter, 1994, p. 84). Firms are thus subject to a growth imperative⁷⁵, meaning that their survival in the market is contingent upon their ability to expand their capital for the purpose of implementing (cost-reducing) innovations⁷⁶ (Castree, 2010; Richters & Siemoneit, 2019; Wood, 2012). Here, the direction of innovation is of central significance. Innovation exhibits a pronounced bias towards labour-saving technologies and automation, as relatively expensive labour inputs are substituted with low-cost combinations of energy, material resources and capital⁷⁷ (Jackson & Victor, 2011; Kümmel, 2011; Richters & Siemoneit, 2019). Rising labour productivity essentially implies that the same economic output can be produced with less labour input, *ceteris paribus*. Economic growth hence becomes necessary to avoid rising unemployment, as the labour productivity gains have to be offset through a macroeconomic expansion of production (Hoffmann & Paulsen, 2020; Jackson & Victor, 2011; Wiedmann et al., 2020). With reference to Marx (1981), Neisser (1942, p. 70) thus describes the “capitalistic process as a race between displacement of labor through technological progress and reabsorption of labor through accumulation”.

Capitalist societies thus find themselves confronted with a profound predicament, the so-called productivity trap (Jackson & Victor, 2011). In a work-centred and work-dependent industrial society (Hoffmann & Paulsen, 2020), the productivity trap gives rise to a political growth imperative: Governments are compelled to pursue politics of growth to avoid technological unemployment and the corollary pressures of high unemployment on public budgets, the latter

⁷⁵ Not all firms are, however, necessarily subject to a growth imperative. Empirical investigations show that small and medium enterprises (SMEs) may be able to circumvent the grow or die logic of competitive markets, especially when operating in niche markets with a strong emphasis on the quality of products and services, respectively (Leonhardt et al., 2017; Liesen et al., 2013).

⁷⁶ The compulsion to re-invest profits with a view to technological innovation does, however, not only occur in competitive markets but also in oligopolistic or monopolistic markets. In such markets, the compulsion to innovate stems from firms’ profit-seeking behaviour: In monopoly capitalism “innovations are typically introduced [...] by giant corporations which act not under the compulsion of competitive pressures but in accordance with careful calculations of the profit-maximizing course” (Baran & Sweezy, 1968, p. 93).

⁷⁷ On the one hand, this direction of innovation is facilitated by the cheap and easy accessibility of ostensibly abundant natural resources, as the “social costs” (Kapp, 1978) of resource depletion and environmental degradation are not internalised (Jackson & Victor, 2011). On the other hand, innovations towards labour-saving technologies are also encouraged by the high cost of labour. Historically, these rising costs (and the implied increases in wages) can be attributed to the social struggles of the working class and the establishment of welfare state arrangements (Röpke, 2010). Moreover, the expensive character of labour is further amplified by the design of taxation systems, which heavily rely on employment-related taxes to fund welfare systems (European Commission & Directorate-General for Taxation and Customs Union, 2022a).

being a result of the contraction of tax revenues and the increased demand for social security provisioning (Richters & Siemoneit, 2019; Wiedmann et al., 2020). Based on these considerations, I conclude that the sphere of employment is indeed growth dependent, whereby the underlying productivity trap represents a first-order growth dependence.

5.2.2 Capital as self-expanding value

In order to investigate the alleged growth dependence of capital, it is instructive to employ a Marxist perspective, as the socioeconomic dynamics of capital accumulation and economic growth have been extensively studied within this tradition of political economy. Whereas classical and neoclassical economists have mostly treated capital as a mere factor of production, capital is better understood as an expression of particular, historically contingent social relations⁷⁸ constitutive of capitalist societies (Ghosh, 2012).

The essential nature of capital in capitalism can be well illuminated by looking at Marx's (1981) description of the economic process. In extended form, Marx's general formula of capital circulation⁷⁹ can be written as follows:

$$M - C \left\{ \begin{array}{l} LP \\ \dots P \dots C' - M + \Delta M \\ MP \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

In a nutshell, the capitalist uses money (M) to buy commodities (C) – that is commodified labour power (LP) and means of production (MP), like raw materials, tools, and machinery – to advance the production (P) of a new commodity (C'). This new commodity is then sold on the market for more money than was originally employed in the production process, i.e. the original money value (M) plus the profit or surplus value⁸⁰ (ΔM). Most importantly, this process does not simply cease after one instance of production. Rather, the final money values will be reinvested by the capitalist given the pressures emanating from competition, thus commencing yet another cycle of

⁷⁸ The two constitutive social relations in capitalism are the wage relation – i.e. the hierarchical social relation between capitalists and labourers, between those that buy and those that sell commodified labour power – and the market relation – i.e. the organisation of commodity production around principles of market exchange mediated by money (Cahen-Fourot, 2022). I will come back to the issue of these two social relations in the final outlook of this thesis (section 7.5).

⁷⁹ Marx's general formula of capital has also been appreciated as an illuminating contribution by John Maynard Keynes (2013). See Dillard (1984) and Foster (2010) for a discussion.

⁸⁰ It should be emphasised at this point that in Marxian political economy, labour represents the exclusive source of value. Hence, the profit must stem from a process of exploitation, in which the surplus value created by labour is appropriated by the capitalist (Harvey, 1985, 2010).

production (Castree, 2010; Harvey, 2010; Sweezy, 1981). Marx's depiction of the circulation of capital thus describes a ceaselessly recurring process, potentially continuing *ad infinitum*. It thus follows that capital – being subject to an imperative of accumulation – can never stand still: “The circulation of money as capital is an end in itself, for the valorization of value takes place only within this constantly renewed movement. The movement of capital is therefore limitless” (Marx, 1981, p. 253).

Thus, from a Marxist perspective, a no-growth or steady-state capitalism constitutes a logical impossibility⁸¹ (Blauwhof, 2012; Harvey, 2010; Lange, 2018; Li, 2007; Magdoff & Foster, 2011; Smith, 2010). Or as Schumpeter (1949, p. 210; emphasis in original) maintains: “Capitalism is a process, stationary capitalism would be a *contradictio in adjecto*”. In that regard, it must be emphasised that, from a Marxist perspective, what is commonly referred to as economic growth simply represents the result of capital accumulation (Andreucci & McDonough, 2015; Blauwhof, 2012; Pineault, 2018; Scarano, 2018; Wood, 2012). It follows that a cessation of economic growth is to be understood as an obstruction of the circulation of capital. Crucially, the corollary of a prolonged impediment of capital accumulation must be tantamount to crises in capitalism (Castree, 2010; Foster et al., 2010; Harvey, 2011; Magdoff & Foster, 2011), as the reproduction of capital is predicated upon profitable opportunities for surplus absorption (Baran & Sweezy, 1968; Foster, 1986; Harvey, 2011). Hence, capital substantially impeded in its reproduction process is inherently dysfunctional in a capitalist economic system, as it cannot fulfil its primary purpose: expansion.

So does an understanding of capital in the sense just elaborated imply a growth dependence of capital? A first intuitive answer might be given in the affirmative. A cessation of economic growth implies an obstruction of the circulation of capital and thus ensuing crises. Moreover, a growing market provides apt opportunities for the absorption of economic surplus and thus aids capital's reproduction (Clarke, 1990). There are, however, two considerable issues with describing capital as growth dependent. First, it seems to be a logically flawed assertion, as economic growth is simply a manifestation of the process of capital accumulation. To argue that capital is dependent on economic growth would thus be to argue that capital is dependent on the expansionary dynamics itself gives rise to in the first place. Second, describing capital as growth dependent seems almost tautological, since the functional purpose of capital is to grow in an endless process of accumulation: “What capital strives for—the purpose of its existence—is its own expansion”

⁸¹ Employing a post-Keynesian perspective, Cahen-Fourot & Lavoie (2016) arrive at a similar conclusion. For a dissenting view, see ecological economist Lawn (2005, 2011).

(Magdoff & Foster, 2011, p. 56). So even if we were to apply a broader understanding of growth dependence not explicitly concerned with dependence on economic growth, we would arrive at the conclusion that capital – being subject to an accumulation imperative – is growth dependent simply by the virtue of being capital.

Even though capital clearly exhibits characteristics of growth dependence, I argue that the notion of growth dependence as advanced by Petschow et al. (2018a) is inapt for properly conceptualising the dynamics of capital in the Marxian sense. Rather, capital may be best understood as *self-expanding value* (Foster, 2002; Klitgaard, 2013; Magdoff & Foster, 2011; Malm, 2013; O'Connor, 1988; Sweezy, 1981), the reproduction of which is dependent on sufficient opportunities for surplus absorption (Baran & Sweezy, 1968; Foster, 1986; Harvey, 2011). Capital as self-expanding value thus represents such a constitutive and fundamental element of capitalism that it seems to transcend characteristics of both growth dependence and growth driver by way of subsuming them in a single entity.

Crucially, this conception of capital also bears illuminating insights pertaining to the growth dependence of employment described in the preceding section. The necessity to introduce cost-reducing and thus labour-displacing innovations is of course itself rooted in the capitalist logic of capital circulation and capital's reproduction through unceasing accumulation. Capital as self-expanding value hence gives rise to the very dynamics that underly the productivity trap and thus the growth dependence of employment. In that regard, capital as self-expanding value seems to lie at the heart of what is oftentimes referred to as the growth imperative of capitalism (Cahen-Fourot, 2022; Ferguson, 2018; M. J. Gordon & Rosenthal, 2003; Magdoff & Foster, 2011; Pineault, 2018; Richters & Siemoneit, 2019; Smith, 2010). Given these considerations, we may conclude that capital as self-expanding value can be seen as the axiomatic starting point for growth dependencies in the capitalist system. In other words, capital as self-expanding value constitutes the quintessential element that – being embedded into capitalist social relations – gives rise to and structurally necessitates economic growth.

5.2.3 Land – They're not making it anymore

As is the case for capital, no explicit treatment of the growth dependence of land exists in the literature. Thus, let us commence the analysis by clarifying what land refers to and which

characteristics render it a distinct factor of production⁸². Employing a rather narrow conception, land may simply be defined as locational or physical space⁸³ (Gaffney, 1994; Ryan-Collins et al., 2017) with a myriad of societal, economic and environmental functions (Pérez-Soba et al., 2008). From an economic point of view, land can thus be described as “scarce space for locating economic production activities, infrastructure and dwellings, as productive soil that provides organic and inorganic materials for agriculture, as a store of assets and resources, and as a source of aesthetic value and amenity services” (Hubacek & van den Bergh, 2006, p. 6).

Land has quite particular characteristics that merit special attention in the light of the present analysis. First, land cannot be produced nor is it reproduceable⁸⁴ (Gaffney, 1994; Polanyi, 2001; Ryan-Collins et al., 2017). In other words: They’re not making it anymore⁸⁵. Second, land is a permanent entity that does not depreciate or wear out over time – even though its attributes may be affected by human (ab)uses (Gaffney, 1994; McCluskey et al., 2005; Ryan-Collins et al., 2017). It follows from these two characteristics that the natural supply of land is essentially fixed (Gaffney, 1994; Mirrlees & Adam, 2011; Ryan-Collins et al., 2017), a distinctive property that has already been appreciated by classical economist David Ricardo, who saw land as “an inexhaustible and nonreproducible agent, unalterably fixed in supply” (Blaug, 1997, p. 80). A fixed supply not only carries with it the theoretical implication of perfect inelasticity (McCluskey et al., 2005); it implies that the supply of land is essentially unalterable, irrespective of all social, economic and environmental dynamics. I thus infer that land – by virtue of its characteristics as space – is strictly growth *independent*⁸⁶. In other words, a cessation of economic growth does not affect the supply of land.

5.2.4 Consumption as a second-order growth dependence

To conclude the analyses in this subchapter, let us now turn to the socioeconomic sphere of consumption. The current literature on growth dependence remains vague at best regarding the case of consumption, as there exists – at least to the best of my knowledge – no illuminating

⁸² Gaffney (1994) provides an extensive overview of land’s characteristics, arguing that land as a production factor is inherently different from capital, a distinction not appreciated by much of neoclassical economics.

⁸³ Crucially, land as space is distinct from the many services it provides (Gaffney, 1994).

⁸⁴ Land reclamation does not *produce* land in the strict sense. When oceans and bodies of water are turned into landfills, this simply represents a reallocation of land to a different use (Gaffney, 1994). Similarly, phenomena such as coastal erosion are not to be considered a loss of land but rather a change of land’s properties.

⁸⁵ The well-known quip “Buy land – they’re not making it anymore” is attributed to Mark Twain (Ryan-Collins et al., 2017).

⁸⁶ It must be emphasised that while the supply of land may be growth independent, the case may be quite different for the value of land. A discussion of land’s growth dependence in terms of value is, however, beyond the scope of this analysis.

treatment of the issue. Røpke (2010, p. 1) almost fleetingly acknowledges that “increasing consumption is dependent on continued economic growth” but does not further elaborate on what essentially constitutes this growth dependence. Similarly, Seidl & Zahrnt (2012) assert that consumption represents a growth dependent social system but fail to properly substantiate this claim, as they primarily focus on the growth-driving dynamics of consumption⁸⁷. It thus seems as though the question of the growth dependence of consumption has not been satisfactorily considered in the post-growth literature.

Consumption and economic growth are interdependent phenomena with strong bidirectionally reinforcing effects (Parrique, 2019; Petschow et al., 2018a; Richters & Siemoneit, 2017; Røpke, 2010; Seidl & Zahrnt, 2012; Wiedmann et al., 2020). If economic growth ceases, aggregate demand declines and so does the extent of consumption. Nonetheless, the question whether consumption is dependent on economic growth is not as straightforward as it may initially seem. Let me elaborate. In market economies, money is ultimately required in order to engage in the consumption of goods and services (Ilmonen, 2011). Hence, the deciding question for the alleged growth dependence of consumption, is where the monetary resources to engage in consumption come from in the first place. Generally speaking, these monetary resources may stem from income derived from the three factors of production, i.e. wages from labour, profits from capital, and rents from land⁸⁸. This of course leads us back to those socioeconomic areas which are themselves being investigated here with a view to their growth dependence. As we have seen, the growth dependence analyses of the three factors of production have yielded varied conclusions. Both employment and capital exhibit characteristics of growth dependence, while land is strictly growth independent. Given that income in the macroeconomic sense comprises wages, profits as well as rents⁸⁹, we may conclude that consumption is – at least to some extent – growth dependent. Analogous to the welfare state, the growth dependence of consumption is a second-order growth dependence.

⁸⁷ For a discussion of the growth-driving dynamics of consumption – in particular positional consumption and habituation effects – see Petschow et al. (2018a).

⁸⁸ There are of course two additional sources of income that are relevant for consumption, which will, however, not be considered here in detail. First, money may of course be borrowed to engage in consumption. The resulting debt, however, is then (or at least should be) serviced by future income. Secondly, the welfare state may provide income support programmes, which are of course financed by the four tax bases under investigation. As the observant reader may realise, a careful consideration of the welfare state as a source of income employed for consumption would result in circular reasoning regarding the issue of growth dependence.

⁸⁹ This of course has interesting distributional implications, which can, however, only be insinuated here. In essence, the consumption of different socioeconomic strata seems to be affected by growth dependence to a varying degree. The monetary resources and thus the ability to consume of low- and middle-income individuals depends to primarily on employment, while wealthier individuals often derive additional income from capital (i.e. profit) and land (i.e. rent). The growth dependence of consumption of individuals is thus co-determined by both the personal and functional income distribution.

5.3 A restatement of the post-growth funding dilemma

Building on the insights developed up until here, I now turn to a brief restatement of the post-growth funding dilemma. As should have become clear by now, the post-growth funding dilemma cannot be aptly comprehended as simply an issue of public finance accounting. Even though the post-growth funding dilemma is to be understood as a fiscal growth dependence of the welfare state, the present analysis indicates that this fiscal growth dependence is a mere epiphenomenon of contradictory dynamics inherent to the political economy of welfare capitalism. Drawing on the insights developed in section 3, the post-growth funding dilemma can be understood as a contradiction of the welfare state, emerging from the state's conflictual double bind to both accumulation and democratic legitimation. In a degrowing economy, this latent feature of welfare capitalism may, however, manifest into a fiscal crisis that substantially jeopardises the integrity of the welfare state as an essential democratic institution.

Moreover, the post-growth funding dilemma essentially constitutes a second-order growth dependence that arises due to the ostensible growth dependencies of the tax bases relevant for welfare state financing. In the preceding section, I thus sought to gauge the growth dependence of labour, capital, land, and consumption. Here, the analysis indicates that land and consumption are not sufficiently growth dependent in and of themselves to qualify as relevant causes of the post-growth funding dilemma. In the case of land, this is due to its fixed supply and its strict growth independence. In the case of consumption, this is due to the fact that consumption is itself dependent on income from the three factors of production and hence subject to a second-order growth dependence. With respect to the sphere of employment, I conclude that its growth dependence represents a significant cause of the post-growth funding dilemma, an insight in line with current literature on the topic (Corlet Walker et al., 2021; Hoffmann & Paulsen, 2020; Petschow et al., 2018a; Richters & Siemoneit, 2019).

In contrast to employment, the role of capital as a cause of the post-growth funding dilemma has not been discussed in the literature on welfare states' growth dependence. The present analysis, however, indicates that capital represents the most constitutive cause of the post-growth funding dilemma for three reasons. First, and perhaps quite obviously, the expansionary logic of capital is – in conjunction with the dominant socio-political position of capitalists – at the root of the state's accumulation imperative. As has been elaborated in section 3, this accumulation imperative is in inherent conflict with the imperative of democratic legitimation, thus giving rise to the post-growth funding dilemma as a latent contradiction of welfare capitalism. Secondly, capital as self-expanding

value has been described as exhibiting features of growth dependence – even though it seems to transcend the concept upon closer consideration. And thirdly, the profit-driven logic surrounding the circulation of capital in a competitive market is what gives rise to the constant need for labour-saving innovations and hence the productivity trap in the first place. In that regard, I maintain that capital – being embedded into capitalist social relations (Cahen-Fourot, 2022) – is what gives rise to the first-order growth dependence of employment, from which in turn emerges the second-order growth dependence of the welfare state.

Given these considerations, we may arrive at a three-layered understanding of the post-growth funding dilemma, with each layer illuminating different aspects of welfare states' growth dependence. On the surface, the post-growth funding dilemma may simply be seen as an expression of a fiscal growth dependence, built on the intuitive notion that – all else being equal – economic activities and hence revenues for welfare state financing will decrease in the context of a degrowing economy. Digging a bit deeper, however, it becomes apparent that the welfare state cannot be considered growth dependent in and of itself but is rather subject to a second-order growth dependence. Here, the second-order growth dependence mainly stems from the first-order growth dependence of employment. At the most fundamental level of understanding, I argue that the post-growth funding dilemma is an inherent feature of welfare capitalism. The post-growth funding dilemma essentially emerges from the social relations of capitalism, whereby capital – understood as self-expanding value – constitutes the axiomatic cause of growth dependencies of all order in the political economy of welfare capitalism.

5.4 The post-growth funding dilemma of the Austrian welfare state

Given the insights gained in the preceding chapters, it is now time to conclude on the research question that was posed at the outset of this thesis: In what ways and to what extent does the funding structure of the Austrian welfare state and its welfare programmes result in a dependence on economic growth? In what follows, I thus highlight how the four tax bases contribute to the post-growth funding dilemma of the Austrian welfare state⁹⁰.

⁹⁰ Recalling the layered understanding of the post-growth funding dilemma described in the preceding section, it must be emphasised that the following considerations refer first and foremost to the *fiscal* dimension of the post-growth funding dilemma. To analyse the tax composition of the Austrian welfare state with a view to its second-order growth dependence is, of course, not to deny the fundamentally structural character of the post-growth funding dilemma but rather to investigate its fiscal manifestation in a national context.

The sphere of employment has been characterised as being subject to a first-order growth dependence, the so-called productivity trap. I hence conclude that the main source of growth dependence of the Austrian welfare state is its pronounced reliance on revenues from the factor labour to fund its social protection expenditures. In that regard, the growth dependence of the Austrian welfare state seems to be closely connected to its character as a conservative-corporatist regime, which is defined – among other things – by the centrality of social security systems in organising and financing social protection. The sphere of consumption is a secondary but nonetheless significant funding source of the Austrian welfare state. Consumption, however, cannot be considered growth dependent in and of itself. Given the limited funding contribution of consumption taxes as well as its second-order growth dependence as a tax base, I infer that the socioeconomic area of consumption is only of secondary significance in engendering the growth dependence of the Austrian welfare state. Land, I have argued, is strictly growth independent as a tax base. As such, funding the welfare state through land taxes may significantly lessen the fiscal pressures emanating from the post-growth funding dilemma. In the case of Austria, the contribution of land to welfare state receipts is, however, so miniscule as to render the dampening effect on welfare state growth dependence almost irrelevant.

Let us now turn to the role of capital, the discussion of which requires a more nuanced elucidation. Similar to consumption, capital contributes little to the funding of the Austrian welfare state compared to labour. Since capital has been described as exhibiting features of growth dependence, we may of course infer that the welfare receipts from capital contribute to the growth dependence of the Austrian welfare state. Upon closer consideration, however, the role of capital for welfare states' growth dependence presents itself as more ambivalent than may initially be apparent. As has been argued in the preceding section, capital as self-expanding value lies at the heart of the state's accumulation imperative and can be seen as the critical element from which growth dependencies in the capitalist system emerge. In that regard, an extensive taxation of capital for the purpose of welfare state funding may weaken the imperative of accumulation vis-à-vis the imperative of democratic legitimation and furthermore strike at the axiomatic starting point of growth dependencies in the capitalist economic system. The nature of capital as a funding source for the welfare state is thus contradictory. In the political economy of welfare capitalism, capital taxation may function both as a source and an inhibitor of welfare state growth dependence. Whether one or the other effect prevails is most likely dependent on the respective extent of capital taxation. It seems quite clear, however, that the current level of capital taxation is generally too insignificant to fundamentally alter the character of capital as self-expanding value. Given these

considerations, I draw the conclusion that capital currently contributes to the growth dependence of the Austrian welfare, as the potential of capital taxation to substantially curtail the dynamics that give rise to welfare states' growth dependence is not realised.

Having scrutinised the tax base composition of welfare state funding in Austria as well as the growth dependencies of the capitalist economic system, we may thus come to the following synoptic answer to my research question⁹¹. The post-growth funding dilemma of the Austrian welfare state stems first and foremost from the central role of labour as a source of revenue. Here, the prevalence of social security systems in Austria plays an important role, as these systems are primarily financed through contributions by labour. Moreover, both consumption and capital contribute to the growth dependence of the Austrian welfare state, even though their role is secondary compared to that of labour. Lastly, the financial contributions of land are too miniscule to considerably reduce the growth dependence of the Austrian welfare state.

6 Policy avenues towards growth independent welfare states

As Schumpeter (1918) already acknowledged more than one hundred years ago, the sphere of fiscal policy is to be understood as both a symptom and a cause of the constitutive qualities and changes that characterise our society. On the one hand, the fiscal structure of welfare state financing is of course symptomatic to the evolution of welfare capitalism as centred around capital accumulation and contingent on continuous economic growth. On the other hand, Schumpeter's understanding of fiscal sociology points to the fact that radical reforms in the sphere of welfare state funding may constitute a leverage point for moving current institutions beyond the growth imperative.

The purpose of this final chapter is hence to give a tentative outlook on how a transformation towards a post-growth welfare state might be initiated and expedited. I have argued in the introduction of this thesis that the reduction of structural growth dependencies is a prerequisite for a profound social-ecological transformation of our society and economy. Given the centrality

⁹¹ I have purposefully refrained from touching upon the question whether the growth dependence of the Austrian welfare state has increased or decreased since 1995. While this question is of course an interesting one, it is hardly possible to provide a substantiated answer. On the one hand, the decreasing contributions of labour to funding the Austrian welfare state indicate a slight reduction of growth dependence. On the other hand, both capital and consumption have increased in importance for funding social protection expenditures, thus pointing towards a minor exacerbation of Austria's post-growth funding dilemma. While I would intuitively argue that the former effect may be stronger than the latter, my analytic approach does not really allow for a proper comparison of the effects. Since the growth dependencies of the tax bases emerge on different structural levels, their effects on the growth dependence of welfare states are hardly comparable and may even be seen as incommensurable.

of welfare states in democratic societies, overcoming the growth dependence of the welfare state is imperative. How this growth dependence may be tackled has, however, been only scarcely investigated in the current literature (Bohnenberger, 2022). My reading of the literature furthermore suggests that those authors who do discuss measures to reduce welfare state growth dependence rarely provide in-depth elucidations on the rationales underlying these measures⁹².

Based on the foregoing analysis, I thus try to briefly outline and substantiate policy measures that may help to tackle the immanent issues of the post-growth funding dilemma⁹³. Since the post-growth funding dilemma constitutes a second-order growth dependence, this of course requires substantial changes in those socioeconomic areas, which are relevant for funding welfare state provisioning. As will become clear in this chapter, the suggested policy measures have the advantage of being generally well compatible with and even conducive to societies' ambitions to expedite a social-ecological transformation towards a post-growth economy. Bohnenberger (2022) notes that a transformation of the welfare state may act as a critical social tipping point triggering a process of large-scale societal transformations (Winkelmann et al., 2022). In that regard, the proposed avenues for reform may act as possible leverage points to instigate what Hirvilammi (2020) calls a "virtuous circle of sustainable welfare". Lastly, the suggested measures are broad in that they apply to the post-growth funding dilemma in its most general form and will hence be more or less relevant for *any* welfare state⁹⁴.

In chapter 3, I have argued that the post-growth funding dilemma essentially emerges from the state's contradictory double bind to accumulation and democratic legitimation. While the structural contradiction between these conflicting state imperatives may remain latent in times of (sufficiently high) economic growth, this contradiction will likely materialise in the form of multidimensional crises when economic growth comes to a halt or ceases altogether. "Crises in social systems", Habermas (1988, p. 2) argues, emerge "through structurally inherent system-imperatives that are incompatible and cannot be hierarchically integrated". In the absence of economic growth,

⁹² The publication by Petschow et al. (2018a) is an exception in that regard. The authors offer a discussion of measures to reduce the growth dependence of social security systems, focusing on the pension system and health insurance in Germany. Here, the authors not only discuss fiscal measures to overcome what I call the post-growth funding dilemma but also highlight measures to tackle issues pertaining to the expenditure and revenue dilemma, respectively.

⁹³ It should be noted that I focus here on measures to overcome welfare state growth dependence in terms of the post-growth funding dilemma. While the other three dilemmas may call for distinct policy measures, the reforms proposed here may nonetheless be relevant for tackling *all* types of welfare state growth dependence.

⁹⁴ Of course, the particularities of the measures discussed would need to be tailored in accordance with the idiosyncratic features of national economies and their welfare states, thus taking into account both the characteristics of social protection systems and the underlying funding structures. Hence, I refrain from suggesting specific tax rates or more detailed modalities of implementing the discussed measures.

continuous capital accumulation can hence only be maintained through crisis, which results in a relocation of monetary values from labour and the state towards capital (Blauwhof, 2012), thus weakening the imperative of democratic legitimation. With respect to the issue of financing welfare states in a post-growth society, the contradiction between accumulation and legitimation is thus likely to manifest in a fiscal crisis of the welfare state and, potentially, its (partial) disintegration.

To overcome the post-growth funding dilemma, it is hence necessary to simultaneously weaken (and ultimately transcend) the imperative of accumulation, while further strengthening the imperative of democratic legitimation. This of course not only implies a redistribution of monetary values but a fundamental restructuring of societal power relations. Ferguson (2018, p. 139) contends that “at a fundamental level, this accumulation-legitimation contradiction reflects the inequitable distribution of resources within society. Overcoming this antinomy without recourse to economic growth, therefore, requires the reduction of inequality”. Given these considerations, we may contend that the post-growth funding dilemma not only constitutes a structural feature of welfare capitalism but is at its core also an expression of multidimensional inequalities and unequal power relations. The positive proposition related to this assertion is, of course, that redistributive measures may constitute a powerful leverage point to overcoming the post-growth funding dilemma⁹⁵. Crucially, such a focus on redistribution is also key in communicating and achieving public acceptance for a post-growth transformation in general, especially among the disadvantaged in society (Paulson & Büchs, 2022).

6.1 Capital: Striking at the heart of the post-growth funding dilemma

Let us commence the discussion with possibly the most elementary redistributive measure: the taxation of capital. With respect to the aim of overcoming the fiscal predicaments pertaining to the post-growth funding dilemma, the taxation of capital serves two main purposes: impeding the process of capital accumulation on the one hand and raising additional revenue for financing the welfare state on the other. Even though I do suggest separate measures for these two purposes, there may well exist substantial synergies. Moreover, the taxation of capital is crucial to limit rentier power (Stratford, 2020) and generally alter the highly unequal power relations between capital and

⁹⁵ Moreover, redistribution will in any way be required in a non-growing economy to prevent rising inequalities (Hartley et al., 2020). The centrality of an equitable distribution for non-growing economies has already been emphasised by John Stuart Mill (2004) in his writings on the stationary state.

labour, which are ultimately the root cause of the antagonisms between accumulation and legitimation.

In the preceding section, the analysis of capital as self-expanding value has led to the conclusion that capital is the axiomatic starting point of structural growth dependencies of all order. Moreover, capital in its interrelation with the social relations of capitalism lies at the heart of the states' accumulation imperative. The taxation of capital is hence imperative, as it may impede the process of capital accumulation and thus weaken the very dynamics that give rise to the productivity trap and in turn the second-order growth dependence of the welfare state. In that regard, the proposal by Lange (2018) for a progressive taxation of corporate revenue seems to be a well-suited measure, as it would give rise to diseconomies of scale⁹⁶ that may help to disincentivise investment and inhibit the expansion of firms' production beyond a certain level.

The second rationale for taxing capital is of course the generation of additional revenues for welfare state funding. The central problem here is of course that capital as self-expanding value exhibits features of growth dependence. In other words, taxes from capital may not serve as a stable funding source in a post-growth economy⁹⁷. It should be emphasised, however, that my analysis of capital's growth dependence was very broad in the sense that it neglected how different forms of capital – such as corporate profit, capital gains, wealth, property, and inheritance – may be growth dependent to varying extent. For instance, immovable property such as real estate may still serve as a relatively stable funding source in a post-growth economy⁹⁸. In any case, capital taxes can surely act as a significant source of revenue for the welfare state during the transformation towards a post-growth economy. In the literature dealing with welfare state growth dependence, several forms of capital taxation have been proposed to provide funding for welfare state provisioning in a post-growth context: wealth and property taxes, inheritance taxes, as well as financial transaction taxes (Bailey, 2015; Büchs, 2021; Cattaneo & Vansintjan, 2016; Kubon-Gilke, 2021).

6.2 Labour: Redistributive tax cuts and overcoming the productivity trap

⁹⁶ Further measures to promote diseconomies of scale include increasing the costs of transportation, promoting local instead of global infrastructures, and policies to limit the size of firms (Lange, 2018).

⁹⁷ It should be noted, however, that in a post-growth and hence post-capitalist economic system, capital would almost certainly exhibit characteristics quite different from its contemporary nature as self-expanding value. In that regard, no definitive conclusion can be reached here regarding the growth dependence of capital in a post-growth economy.

⁹⁸ Tax elasticity literature suggests that property taxes are highly inelastic and thus serve as a quite stable source of revenue in times of economic downturns (Afonso, 2017; Hou & Seligman, 2007; McCubbins & Seljan, 2010).

The socioeconomic area of employment has been characterised as being subject to a first-order growth dependence arising from the so-called productivity trap. Since welfare states are primarily financed through taxes and social contributions stemming from the factor labour, the productivity trap constitutes a major contributing dynamic to the post-growth funding dilemma. In that regard, my analysis indicates two meaningful avenues to reduce the growth dependence of the welfare state: a redistributive reduction of taxes and social contributions on labour as well as measures to overcome the growth dependence of employment.

The rationale underlying the first proposition is quite intuitive: If employment is to be considered a growth dependent socioeconomic area, then we may reduce the growth dependence of the welfare state by simply decreasing the extent to which welfare states are financed through taxes and social contributions on labour. Here, Köppl & Schratzenstaller's (2021) call for an employment-friendly tax system is instructive. Essentially, the authors argue for a redistributive reduction of the tax burden on labour and hence recommend a lowering of both personal income taxes and social contributions for low- and middle incomes. The apparent problem with this approach is, however, that it would mean diminished revenues for welfare state funding. To offset this potential decrease of revenues, a reduction of labour taxes and social contributions should be accompanied by hikes of capital, land, and environmental taxes as well as progressive consumption taxes.

The second avenue for reducing the growth dependence of the welfare state is to tackle the growth dependence of employment. In section 5.2.1, it was argued that the productivity trap is the corollary of a general bias of innovation towards labour-saving technologies, which results from the competitive logic of capitalist markets. With respect to this issue, four solution approaches are prominently discussed in the literature. The first of these measures is the well-known proposal to translate labour productivity growth into reduced working hours. Measures of working time reduction⁹⁹ may help to maintain stable employment in a non-growing or degrowing economy by redistributing work more equally among the population (Ferguson, 2018; Jackson & Victor, 2011; Kallis et al., 2018; Lange, 2018; Parrique, 2019; Zwickl et al., 2016).

⁹⁹ Of course, the question of (the extent of) wage compensation is crucial for working time reduction policies. In post-growth and post-work literature, working time reductions with *no* decline in wages are often advocated for (Aronowitz et al., 1998; Kallis et al., 2013; Weeks, 2011). In that regard, Kallis et al. (2013, p. 1561) argue that reduced working time with proportional pay cuts would amount to “a policy of regressive redistribution from labor to capital”. Moreover, full wage compensation is of course crucial, as low-income earners might otherwise not be able to afford a reduction of working time.

The trend towards labour-saving innovations is furthermore facilitated by the availability and cheap access to natural resources, in particular fossil fuels (Altvater, 2005; Schnaiberg, 1980). Hence, a second approach to tackling the productivity trap is to change the relative prices of factor inputs. Here, environmental taxes¹⁰⁰ – coupled with the aforementioned reduction of the tax burden of labour – can help to amend the direction of technological change towards less capital-intensive and hence energy-saving innovations (Lange, 2018; Petschow et al., 2018a). Moreover, such environmental taxes may contribute to the funding of the welfare state in the course of a post-growth transformation (Bailey, 2015). Crucially, the respective tax rates should be set to rise as the tax bases (i.e. the environmentally harmful modes of production and consumption) diminish over time as a result of effective taxation (Ferguson, 2018).

The third measure is concerned with altering the composition of the economy and builds on the fact that much of employment currently takes place in capital- and energy-intensive sectors such as manufacturing. A structural shift of the economy towards more labour-intensive sectors might therefore help to tackle the productivity trap and thus reduce the growth dependence of employment (Jackson & Victor, 2011). In that regard, Ferguson (2018) suggests to increase employment opportunities in the service, public¹⁰¹ and cooperative sector.

Lastly, a fourth measure pertains to supporting the collectivisation of firms towards workers-based ownership structures (Lange, 2018). Crucially, such collective and democratically governed ownership structures are well compatible with the aforementioned measures to tackle the productivity trap. Most importantly, collectively owned firms have an immanent motivation to avoid laying off workers. Lange (2018) maintains that such firms would hence direct their innovations primarily towards energy-saving technology, especially in the context of high energy costs achieved through environmental taxation. If labour productivity gains are nonetheless realised, these may be translated into reduced working hours. Moreover, production in collectively owned firms precludes exploitation and hence the extraction of surplus value since the workers themselves have ownership over the means of production. In conjunction with diseconomies of scale discussed in the preceding section, this may substantially impede on capital accumulation (Lange, 2018), thus weakening the very dynamics that give rise to growth dependencies in the capitalist system.

¹⁰⁰ Ideally, such environmental taxes are developed and implemented in conjunction with eco-social policies to avoid regressive distributional impacts (Gough, 2013, 2017).

¹⁰¹ Increasing employment in the public sector may be well compatible with the notion of a job guarantee (Unti, 2015).

6.3 Land: The growth independent tax base

With respect to land, the policy implications are quite evident. Due to its fixed supply, land is inherently growth independent. In other words, the underlying tax base remains fixed independent of economic fluctuations. This characteristic of land of course makes it a suitable – if not perfect – tax base for funding post-growth welfare states¹⁰². Accordingly, the taxation of land has been proposed as a meaningful measure to generate revenues for welfare states in a post-growth context (Bailey, 2015; Büchs, 2021; Petschow et al., 2018a). Here, a land-value tax¹⁰³ represents a meaningful policy to reduce the growth dependence of the welfare state, as it offers potential for significant revenue generation (Gaffney, 2009). Furthermore, a land-value tax may help to inhibit excessive rent extraction, thereby limiting rentier power. In the context of a social-ecological transformation, limiting the socio-political power of rentiers is crucial according to Stratford (2020), since concentrated rentier power currently hinders effective political action to reduce growth dependencies¹⁰⁴.

6.4 Consumption: Auxiliary measures

In section 5.2.4, it was argued that the socioeconomic area of consumption is second-order growth dependent, since consumption essentially depends on income derived from the three factors of production. In that regard, my analysis indicates that the aforementioned measures pertaining to labour, capital, and land should take precedence over particular reforms in the sphere of consumption. Nonetheless, measures in the sphere of consumption can have an auxiliary function in supporting the proposed reforms in the socioeconomic areas discussed above. First, a more progressive design of value-added taxes and higher tax rates on luxury goods (Alexander & Gleeson, 2019; Murphy, 2013) may help to offset diminishing revenues resulting from lowering the tax burden on labour. And secondly, environmental taxation in the form of taxes on energy and resource consumption may help to alter the direction of technological change and thus

¹⁰² Even though land as a tax base may be perfectly growth independent, the actual revenues generated from land taxation would to a large extent depend on the value of land. Even though it may be fair to say that land prices may cease to grow as markedly as is currently the case, it is difficult to make a substantiated guess on how exactly land prices might develop in a post-growth economic system. In other words, the actual revenue generating capacities of land taxes in a post-growth economy are subject to a great deal of uncertainty. This uncertainty regarding the potentials to fund post-growth welfare states does, however, apply to all tax bases discussed here.

¹⁰³ The land-value tax is commonly associated with Henry George (2006) as one of its main proponents.

¹⁰⁴ For instance, Stratford (2020) contends that the unequal distribution of land and other rent-bearing assets stands in the way of an equitable implementation of working time reduction measures. Here, the unequal power relations associated with concentrated rentier power may prevent an equitable implementation of working time reduction measures, as labour productivity gains may only be passed on to workers with significant reductions in wages.

contribute to overcoming the productivity trap., while also providing additional revenues that may be used to finance the welfare state (Petschow et al., 2018a).

7 Conclusion and discussion

In this concluding section, I first condense the findings of this thesis into a brief synopsis. Following this conclusion, I discuss what general insights we may draw from my analysis of the post-growth funding dilemma. Subsequently, I discuss the analytic limitations of my thesis and outline fruitful avenues for further research in the field of welfare state growth dependence. I proceed by looking forward into the potential future of a post-growth society and consider the idea of a socially just downscaling of the welfare state. Lastly, I provide a brief outlook and discuss how a post-growth transformation may involve a fundamental alteration of the social relations of capitalism.

7.1 Conclusion

How can humanity secure the satisfaction of current and future generations' basic needs whilst safeguarding the ecological integrity of the Earth system? This is the question that was posed at the outset of this thesis. Throughout this analysis, I have argued that only a social-ecological transformation towards a post-growth society will be able to tackle the myriad of challenges associated with answering this question. Here, the welfare state – as an elementary institution of democratic societies – must play a pivotal role in facilitating and supporting the necessary transformative processes. The manifold eco-social policies, which are currently gaining increasing attention in the sustainable welfare literature, are a case in point (Bohnenberger, 2020; Gough, 2015a, 2017, 2019; Koch, 2018, 2021; Koch & Mont, 2016; Lindellee et al., 2021; Stamm et al., 2020).

I have argued that structural growth dependencies represent a substantial obstacle to realising a profound social-ecological transformation that transcends the growth imperative inherent to the political economy of the capitalist system¹⁰⁵. How this growth dependence is constituted in the

¹⁰⁵ Again, it must be emphasised that the reduction of growth dependence also represents a meaningful policy objective for growth-centred economic systems, since less growth dependent societal institutions are more resilient in terms of dealing with recurring economic crises and trends of secular stagnation. The reduction of structural growth dependencies should thus be a top priority of governments and policymakers, irrespective of the position assumed regarding the desirability and feasibility of further economic growth.

case of the welfare state remains, however, insufficiently investigated in the post-growth literature. In chapter 2, I have thus tried to improve on our understanding of welfare state growth dependence by developing an intuitive typology grounded in a comprehensive review of literature in the field. Here, I have identified and delineated four distinct types of welfare state growth dependence: (i) the expenditure dilemma, (ii) the revenue dilemma, (iii) the automatic stabiliser dilemma, and (iv) the post-growth funding dilemma.

Due to its fundamental relevance for a social-ecological transformation, I have chosen to investigate the post-growth funding dilemma and its underlying causes in more detail in the remainder of this thesis. The insights developed have culminated in a layered and nuanced understanding of the post-growth funding dilemma. First, the post-growth funding dilemma constitutes a fiscal growth dependence of the welfare state. Second, the post-growth funding dilemma is a second-order growth dependence, arising due to structural growth dependencies of the tax bases relevant for welfare state funding. And third, the post-growth funding dilemma is a latent structural feature as well as an emergent property of welfare capitalism, rooted in the expansionary nature of capital and the social relations of capitalism. To acknowledge the structural nature of the post-growth funding dilemma is, however, not to deny the possibility for change. The post-growth funding dilemma may also be comprehended as an expression of the unequal distribution of resources and political power in contemporary welfare capitalism. A radical reduction of inequalities in all areas of society not only constitutes a meaningful discursive framing for a post-growth transformation but may indeed help to facilitate the supersession of the accumulation imperative by the imperative of democratic legitimation.

Apart from these theoretical insights, I have tried to investigate how the post-growth funding dilemma as a structural feature of welfare capitalism manifests in a fiscal growth dependence of the Austrian welfare state. To the best of my knowledge, this thesis offers the first country-based exploration of the post-growth funding dilemma based on an in-depth analysis of the tax base composition of welfare state funding. Given the growth dependence of employment, I have concluded that the Austrian welfare state is fiscally growth dependent due to its substantial reliance on taxes and social contributions from labour to fund social protection expenditures. Moreover, the funding contributions of both consumption and capital – even though only of secondary importance compared to labour – further exacerbate the growth dependence of the Austrian welfare state. Lastly, land taxes are too insignificant in extent to substantially reduce growth dependence of the Austrian welfare state.

Furthermore, this thesis has culminated in a series of insights regarding the various growth dependencies in the current economic system. Rather than once again discuss them here in detail, the insights are condensed into table 2. The table also includes the political implications that follow from the growth dependence analysis as well as the suggested policy avenues described in chapter 6.

Table 2: The growth dependencies of welfare capitalism

Area	Order of growth dependence	Underlying causes	Political Implications	Policy avenues
Capital	Axiomatic	Capital as self-expanding value coupled with the social relations of capitalism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weaken accumulation imperative and curtail circulation of capital - Alter unequal power relations - Generate revenue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Progressive corporate income tax - Taxes on wealth, (immobile) property, inheritance, and financial transactions
Labour	First-order	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Productivity trap - Capital as self-expanding value 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce tax burden of labour - Reduce growth dependence of employment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce taxes and social contributions for low- and middle incomes - Working time reduction policies - Environmental taxes to change relative factor prices - Structural shift to low-productivity sectors - Collective firm ownership
Consumption	Second-order	Dependent on income from the three factors of production	Auxiliary support for other reforms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Progressive value-added taxes - Environmental taxes
Land	Growth independent	Fixed supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generate revenue - Limit rent-extraction 	Increase/Introduce land value taxes
Welfare state	Second-order	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary fiscal dependence on labour - Secondary fiscal dependence on consumption and capital - Capital as self-expanding value 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduce inequalities - Shift welfare state funding composition from labour to capital and land 	Redistributive measures

Note: Own representation.

7.2 Discussion: General implications for the growth dependence of welfare states

What general insights may we draw from the explorative analysis of the post-growth funding dilemma and its manifestation in the case of the Austrian welfare state? This is the question I seek to briefly discuss in this section. While we may not directly generalise the insights pertaining to the case of the Austrian welfare state, it may be well possible to transpose some lines of argumentation to reach more general – even though tentative – conclusions. Here, I will primarily draw on the basic assertion that social contributions and taxes represent the primary funding modes for welfare provisioning (Cichon et al., 2004; Manow, 2010; Morel & Palme, 2018; Obinger, 2021; Schmitt et al., 2020). In that regard, a distinction can also be drawn between Bismarckian welfare states (e.g. Austria, France, Germany), which are mainly financed by social contributions, and Beveridgean welfare states (e.g. Denmark, Ireland, Sweden), which rely primarily on general government's tax revenue (Bonoli, 1997; Morel & Palme, 2018). Building on these considerations, I will try to illuminate the potential implications of these distinctions for the post-growth funding dilemma of the welfare state.

In the sustainable welfare literature, the question has been raised whether different welfare state funding regimes may be associated with a varying degree of growth dependence. Büchs & Koch (2017, p. 29) assert that the “distinction between contribution-based and tax-based funding of welfare programmes appears to give ground to the argument that [...] contribution-based systems may react more directly than tax-based ones to market swings”. While this question cannot be answered conclusively here, we maintain that social security systems are by definition mainly financed by labour, a socioeconomic area subject to growth dependence. In that regard, a tentative conclusion may be that Bismarckian welfare states are more susceptible to issues pertaining to the post-growth funding dilemma than Beveridgean welfare states, as the latter tend to be more diverse in terms of their tax base composition.

Nonetheless, it must be emphasised that the Bismarck-Beveridge distinction is not a dichotomy but rather reflects a continuum regarding the relative importance of social contributions and taxes for welfare state funding, respectively (Bonoli, 1997). The assertion that Bismarckian welfare states may be more prone to growth dependence must thus be taken with a pinch of salt. Certainly, the way in which the post-growth funding dilemma unfolds is not only dependent on the country's respective funding regime, but ultimately depends on the idiosyncratic tax base composition of welfare state funding. It follows that, in any case, the post-growth funding dilemma manifests in heterogeneous ways for different countries.

The above line of argumentation regarding the distinction between social contribution-based and tax-based financing may furthermore be extended to single social protection systems, as the mode of funding is oftentimes closely connected to the nature of particular welfare programmes (Cichon et al., 2004; Morel & Palme, 2018). While there exist areas of social protection that are fully financed by either social contributions or taxes, most social protection systems actually exhibit a mixed funding structure (Cichon et al., 2004). In line with the argumentation above, we may tentatively assert that a higher share of social contribution-based funding is associated with a higher susceptibility to growth dependence, and vice versa. Moreover, the aforementioned funding mode distinction also pertains to the various areas of welfare state provisioning (e.g. old-age, unemployment, sickness and health care, et cetera) (Schmitt et al., 2020), indicating that these areas may be subject to growth dependence to varying extent. Again, however, a more definitive conclusion on the growth dependence of different social protection systems and provisioning areas must consider the concrete funding composition and the country-specific context.

The distinction between Bismarckian and Beveridgean funding regimes may furthermore be crucial with respect to governments' political capacities to deal with the fiscal implications of a post-growth transformation of the welfare state. Historically, social contribution-based systems have been less susceptible to retrenchment, given that their funding is not primarily dependent on government's budgetary deliberations. Tax-financed systems, on the other hand, are less stable, as they experience heightened political pressures to cut back on welfare state provisioning when confronted with budgetary predicaments (Manow, 2010; Morel & Palme, 2018). This may indicate that in the course of a post-growth transformation – with its apparent fiscal pressures – the welfare state may be less likely to retrench in Bismarckian welfare states, given the centrality and higher stability of social protection systems (Büchs & Koch, 2017). While this higher resilience of Bismarckian welfare states may be a positive feature in the context of a post-growth transformation, it does, however, come at the price of a higher susceptibility to growth dependence as discussed above.

7.3 Limitations

The investigation of the post-growth funding dilemma in this thesis has, in essence, been an exploratory undertaking. Given the sparse state of the literature on welfare state growth dependence, I think that this exploratory approach and the investigation of the Austrian welfare

state as a case study have been a suitable means to illuminate blind spots in current discussions surrounding post-growth, sustainable welfare, and welfare states beyond growth. Nonetheless, my thesis is subject to several limitations, which shall be discussed in the following.

The most salient limitation of this thesis is that I have restricted my analysis to an investigation of only a single case, namely the Austrian welfare state. The investigation of only one welfare state, of course, reduces the scope in which the analytic conclusions can be generalised. In essence, every welfare state is different and so are the particular compositions of welfare state funding. A more encompassing analysis of welfare states' growth dependence would have been beneficial in terms of strengthening the theoretical and practical implications of my analysis. In that regard, a certainly fruitful avenue for future research is to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the post-growth funding dilemma covering a large sample of welfare states. Here, it may be especially interesting to investigate the post-growth funding dilemma in emerging welfare states (Castles et al., 2010), in which the contradiction between accumulation and democratic legitimation may unfold in distinct ways. Despite these considerations, I believe that the case study approach in conjunction with the explorative nature of my analysis has its merits in terms of illuminating how future research on welfare state growth dependence may be conducted. In that regard, this thesis may form a helpful starting point to develop a more sophisticated methodological approach to studying the post-growth funding dilemma in a comprehensive manner.

The analytic rigour of this thesis is further limited by the following considerations pertaining to the growth dependence analysis conducted in section 5.2. Most importantly, my analysis of the socioeconomic areas of employment, capital, land, and consumption has been quite general, oftentimes drawing on Marxist political economy in the hopes of generating insights (relatively) well applicable to all capitalist economies. Nonetheless, it must be acknowledged that capitalism is diverse, and so is its political economy in terms of national institutional arrangements and embeddedness into varying socioeconomic contexts (Buch-Hansen, 2014; Cahen-Fourot, 2020; Hall & Soskice, 2001). For instance, the extent of growth dependence in the sphere of employment may vary among different countries, as empirical research indicates a high level of national heterogeneity for the Okun coefficient – i.e. the responsiveness of (un)employment to changes in macroeconomic output (Ball et al., 2019). In that regard, the severeness of the productivity trap may differ among countries given heterogenous institutional arrangements, which affect the outcomes on national labour markets. Future research may thus profit from taking into account the various ways in which growth dependencies may unfold in specific national contexts.

Another issue pertains to the growth dependence analysis of capital. For the present purpose, I have deemed it most apt to employ a Marxist perspective to investigate the alleged growth dependence of capital. In doing so, I have certainly abstracted from the more manifest types of capital that we encounter in the realities of the economy. It is apparent that corporate profits, capital gains, financial wealth, immobile property, and inheritances are quite heterogeneous forms of capital. A close consideration of their varying constitutions would have certainly resulted in a more nuanced growth dependence analysis that would have strengthened the theoretical argument presented as well as the political implications derived. Given that taxes on capital are oftentimes advocated for in the context of a post-growth transformation of the welfare state, it is up to future research to further substantiate this line of argumentation by investigating how different capitals may be growth dependent to varying extent. Only then will it be possible to gauge more precisely the capacity of capital taxes to generate revenue in a post-growth society.

Moreover, I want to bring the reader's attention to another analytical issue. In the course of writing this thesis, a recurring question has concerned the problem of how to gauge the severity of the post-growth funding dilemma, especially when it comes to comparisons among different welfare states or over time. Since the post-growth funding dilemma is rooted in the respective tax base composition of the welfare state, the problem ultimately comes down to the question if the growth dependencies of labour, capital, land, and consumption are assumed to be commensurable. Comparing the growth dependencies of the tax bases is, however, not always straightforward, given that their growth dependencies emerge on different structural levels in the political economy of welfare capitalism, with intricate interdependencies¹⁰⁶. Hence, both the severity of the post-growth funding dilemma as well as the efficacies of political measures to tackle it are difficult to evaluate let alone quantify and compare. In that regard, the analytic nature of my growth dependence analysis allows only for a rather vague comparative evaluation of the post-growth funding dilemma. Even though the growth dependencies of the tax bases may not be entirely

¹⁰⁶ Clearly, some comparative inferences may be more straightforward than others. For instance, a higher dependence on labour is most probably associated with higher welfare state growth dependence. Conversely, we can infer that a higher share of land taxes reduces growth dependence. Such argumentation is, however, more complicated with respect to capital. As has been elaborated in section 5.4, the role of capital for the post-growth funding dilemma is quite ambivalent, as it may both contribute to and weaken growth dependence depending on the actual extent of capital's contribution to welfare state funding. Empirically, it may be quite difficult to gauge whether one or the other effect is stronger, thus seriously complicating comparative inferences involving changes of capital's contributions. And of course, things get even more complicated if we consider differences or changes in the tax base composition of welfare state funding as a whole. Given this difficulty, I have refrained from providing a definite evaluation of the severity of Austria's post-growth funding dilemma over time in section 5.4.

incommensurable, the lack of proper comparability represents a significant limitation to my analysis.

Lastly, I want to discuss an assumption that has been pivotal to the way in which the issue of welfare state growth dependence has been analysed: the issue of debt financing. As Obinger (2021) rightly notes, welfare state expenditures may also be financed via public borrowing. I have, however, ruled out this possibility as a meaningful strategy to tackle the fiscal growth dependencies of the welfare state. On the one hand, I have done so for the sake of the argument I sought to develop in this thesis, since accepting that indefinite public borrowing represents a feasible solution to the fiscal predicaments of the (post-growth) welfare state would have rendered the discussion of a fiscal growth dependence obsolete altogether. On the other hand, there are good reasons why large-scale deficit funding of the welfare state may be incompatible with the ambitions to expedite a post-growth transformation.

First, fiscal deficits pertaining to the welfare state and the corollary accumulation of debt compel governments and politicians to pursue politics of growth (Seidl & Zahrnt, 2010b). In that regard, high debt-to-GDP ratios give rise to a political growth imperative, as debt reduction becomes exceedingly difficult in a no-growth economic environment (Stratford, 2020). Secondly, interest payments accruing to borrowing increase state expenditures in the future (Farnsworth & Irving, 2018; O'Connor, 2002), which in turn necessitates economic growth, *ceteris paribus*. In that regard, large-scale deficit funding of welfare state expenditures may be considered fiscally unsustainable and economically unviable in a non-growing economy, especially in the long-term (Bailey, 2015; Corlet Walker et al., 2021). Thirdly, economic growth represents a weighty macroeconomic indicator in determining the credit worthiness and lending conditions of a country (Seidl & Zahrnt, 2010b). A post-growth transformation might thus be accompanied by “capricious and potentially punitive reactions of the financial markets and the credit ratings agencies, which could potentially heighten the cost of borrowing” (Bailey, 2015, p. 799). And lastly, I am of the conviction that the fiscal reforms discussed in section 6 are better suited to tackling the post-growth funding dilemma than continuous debt financing, since the proposed policy avenues seem to align very well with the ambitions to expedite a social-ecological transformation in general. In that regard, funding of the welfare state without recourse to public borrowing may be pivotal in a transformation towards a post-growth economy.

Nonetheless, not considering public borrowing as an option for welfare state funding may be seen as a limitation to my argument. First, deficit funding may serve as a complimentary and temporary financing strategy during a post-growth transformation. For instance, public borrowing may be necessary to fill unforeseen funding gaps in the early stages of a post-growth transformation, as governments' budget deliberations are confronted with substantial uncertainties emanating from the interdependent transformative processes taking place in the economy. From a more theoretical perspective, it should also be emphasised that ruling out deficit funding as a feasible solution to the fiscal predicaments of a post-growth economy is at odds with conclusions reached by Modern Monetary Theory (MMT), particularly the notion that there exists no financial constraints to fiscal policy if the country in question also acts as a sovereign issuer of its own fiat currency (Chohan, 2020; Lawn, 2010; Mitchell et al., 2019). Moreover, deficit financing may be more feasible when considering controversial practices such as debt cancellation (Balibar, 2013; Büscher et al., 2021) and monetary financing (Turner, 2015). Lastly, one should consider that the contemporary financial and monetary institutions are quite certain to undergo a fundamental restructuring in the course of a post-growth transformation, which may increase the economic and political feasibility of funding the welfare state through deficits.

7.4 Avenues for further research

Beyond these limitations, my engagement with the quite broad subject matter of welfare state growth dependence has raised further issues that I believe warrant further research. First of all, and most fundamentally, we need to further expand on our understanding of welfare state growth dependence in its most basic terms. While I hope that my typology may help to delineate more clearly the issue of welfare state growth dependence, the single dilemmas and their constituting dynamics still require future scientific scrutiny. How do the dilemmas of welfare state growth dependence unfold in particular national and institutional contexts? Which dynamics are the most salient in terms of contributing to the severeness of the dilemmas? And what kind of policy measures may be suitable to tackle the issues pertaining to the single dilemmas? These are some of the questions that future research may consider.

Future research may also concern itself with a more differentiated analysis of the post-growth funding dilemma. Welfare states comprise services and benefits in various areas and consist of several distinct social protection systems. The analysis of the post-growth funding dilemma may thus be extended by investigating the tax base composition of single social protection systems and

areas of provisioning, respectively. This would yield an even more differentiated picture regarding the growth dependence of welfare states by way of analysing its constituent parts. Such an in-depth analysis of welfare state growth dependence further seems meaningful insofar as it would allow for the formulation of more specific and tailored policy measures aimed at tackling the post-growth funding dilemma. A more meticulous study of the post-growth funding dilemma thus constitutes a meaningful direction for further research.

Another crucial issue is the formulation of well-substantiated policy proposals that may help to overcome the post-growth funding dilemma. While this thesis has sought to provide a tentative overview of potential avenues towards growth independent welfare states, there remains substantial need for further investigation. To inform effective policymaking for welfare states beyond growth first of all requires a better understanding of how tax revenues might react in the course of a post-growth transformation. Here, future research may build on instances of macroeconomic modelling (D'Alessandro et al., 2020; Jackson & Victor, 2020) to investigate in more detail the effects of a post-growth transformation and its related policies on the tax base composition of welfare state receipts, as also suggested by Corlet Walker et al. (2021). Moreover, literature on tax elasticities suggests that tax revenues decreases more sharply in recessions than their underlying tax bases (Sancak et al., 2010). In that regard, it may prove meaningful to investigate in detail how different tax bases and their respective revenue streams may react to economic downturns and a post-growth scenario, respectively. Further research in this area may hence focus on tax policies suggested in the literature on welfare state growth dependence to substantiate more clearly which taxes may provide (more or less) stable revenues in a post-growth economy. Building on these insights, more concrete and well-substantiated policy measures to overcome the post-growth funding dilemma may be developed.

From a fiscal sociology perspective, it may be scrutinised whether some welfare regimes may be more likely to adopt growth dependence reducing policy measures. In chapter 6, I have argued that overcoming the post-growth funding dilemma necessitates a substantial shift of welfare state funding from labour towards capital and land and hence a shift from social contributions to taxes. The question thus arises, whether contribution-based or tax-based funding systems may be more open to enact the required fiscal reforms. Future research may thus ask what institutional and political barriers governments in different welfare regimes face when considering the implementation of policies to reduce welfare state growth dependence.

Lastly, and perhaps quite obviously, my approach of disentangling the tax base composition of funding may be extended to analyse the fiscal growth dependence of public budgets more generally. In that regard, it may be sensible to investigate in how far state expenses in other important areas such as education, defence, infrastructure, et cetera are dependent on economic growth. Beyond these fiscal considerations, I believe that these areas further deserve an in-depth analysis from a political economy perspective to illuminate the institutional context, in which these state functions are embedded. As we have seen with respect to the welfare state, this is crucial to comprehend the intricate nature of growth dependence in capitalist societies.

7.5 Looking forward: A socially just downscaling of the welfare state?

Before concluding this thesis, let us venture to look forward into how welfare states may look like in a (hopefully not so distant) post-growth future. While this thesis has been primarily concerned with the intricate fiscal issues of post-growth welfare states and how these may be addressed, it is certain that more substantial transformations of the welfare state will occur during a social-ecological transformation.

The issue I would like to touch upon is quite a delicate one, having been the subject of much political and scholarly contention: the size of the welfare state and the question of retrenchment. This issue gains yet another dimension of significance in the context of social-ecological crises, which require societies to radically reduce their socio-metabolic throughput to stay within planetary boundaries. Indeed, it is a legitimate question whether a post-growth transformation in the Global North would be accompanied by a diminishing role and size of the welfare state. In that regard, Bailey (2015, p. 802) contends that “moving beyond growth seemingly precipitates an invidious degree of public sector retrenchment”. Conversely, a myriad of scholars maintain that welfare states must play a pivotal role for a just transition towards a sustainable economic system (Bailey, 2015; Bohnenberger, 2020; Gough, 2017; Hirvilammi, 2020; Koch, 2021). Following Parrique (2019) and Cattaneo & Vansintjan (2016), we may try to solve this seeming contradiction by thinking about the social-ecological transformation and the role of the welfare state therein in terms of two successive phases.

In essence, the first phase pertains to the early years of a post-growth transformation. Here, societies implement the necessary political measures that allow them to decrease their economic activities to sustainable levels in a socially just manner. This, of course, entails the overcoming of growth dependencies. During this possibly turbulent transitional phase, the welfare state will be

more than ever required to enact eco-social policies and alleviate the risks associated with the ongoing ecological crises. In that regard, the start of a post-growth transformation should indeed be characterised by an increased need for and an extension of welfare state provisioning. For the welfare state to fulfil its crucial role in this first phase of the transformation, it is imperative to secure the fiscal basis of welfare state provisioning.

Following this first transitional phase, we may think of the second phase as the realisation phase of a post-growth society. Given that growth dependencies have been overcome, this second phase is characterised by an on-going downscaling of economic activities and socio-metabolic throughput in line with planetary boundaries. Like all societal institutions, the welfare state will undergo a substantial restructuring and transformation in this phase. While it may be possible to offset diminishing welfare state receipts through redistributive fiscal measures in the first phase, this strategy cannot be employed indefinitely given the necessity of a radical degrowing of the economy¹⁰⁷. It is thus in this second phase that welfare state retrenchment will most likely occur as the corollary of a contraction of economic activities (Koch, 2020; Quilley & Zywert, 2019). In that regard, Koch (2020, p. 128f.) maintains that welfare states “may be recalibrated – and in all likelihood downscaled – to meet human needs within environmental limits”. Such welfare state retrenchment, however, ought to be different from contemporary forms of welfare state retrenchment, similar to how degrowth is inherently distinct from a recession. In that regard, it may be more appropriate to speak of a *socially just downscaling of the welfare state* – or what Bailey (2015, p. 808) terms “progressive modes of welfare state retrenchment” – in this second phase of the social ecological transformation.

While such a socially just downscaling of the welfare state ultimately constitutes an ecological necessity, it may also be facilitated by the fundamental changes occurring in the course of a social-ecological transformation. In the context of a post-growth – and hence post-capitalist – society, people would no longer be subjected to the ills of an exploitative and highly unequal capitalist economic system, thus resulting in a diminishing need for welfare state provisioning in the first place. In that regard, a downscaled welfare state may be “entirely acceptable as long as it is embedded with a wider economic system which provides relatively egalitarian outcomes without such a reliance on the state” (Bailey, 2015, p. 808).

¹⁰⁷ The magnitude of the necessary reductions is indeed substantial. According to Trainer (2021), high-income countries would be required to reduce their per capita resource use and environmental impacts – and thus the extent of production and consumption – by around 90 %.

How might such a socially just downscaling of the welfare state look like? Even though it is, of course, impossible to answer this question in advance, some tentative considerations may be outlined. First of all, the focus of social policies may shift from a primarily curative and compensatory logic towards an emphasis on prevention (Berghman et al., 2018; Gough, 2015a). Secondly, a post-growth welfare state may be increasingly concerned with *predistribution* rather than ex-post redistribution (O'Neill, 2020). Thirdly, welfare provisioning may become gradually more decentralised and place-bound in a post-growth economy. Drawing on the concept of polycentric governance developed by Elinor Ostrom (2009), post-growth scholars have argued for welfare provisioning to be organised in cooperative governance structures comprising multiple stakeholders across the national, regional, and local level (Cattaneo & Vansintjan, 2016; Corlet Walker et al., 2021). Here, the importance of the local level may grow significantly during a socially just downscaling of the welfare state. In that regard, Quilley & Zywert (2019) stress that for an economic system to operate within ecological limits large parts of welfare provisioning would have to be organised in terms of place-bound and reciprocal institutions centred around families and communities as central units¹⁰⁸.

A profound social-ecological transformation of our society is likely to pertain to the welfare state in similar significance. In that regard, I would deem it quite plausible that a degrowing economic system may necessarily be accompanied by an equal degrowing of centralised welfare state provisioning. If such a retrenchment of the welfare state indeed represents the corollary of our ambitions to reduce societies' socio-metabolic throughput to sustainable levels, then it is imperative to orchestrate the downscaling of the welfare state in a socially just and democratic manner.

7.6 Outlook: Beyond the social relations of capitalism

A common Marxist critique directed at post-growth scholars is the fetishisation of economic growth as the central issue of concern regarding a social-ecological transformation (Foster, 2011a; Pirgmaier & Steinberger, 2019). And it is indeed a valid point that concepts such as post-growth and degrowth may be “shooting at the wrong target” (Parrique, 2019, p. 425) by confusing the symptom (economic growth) with the underlying cause (capital accumulation). Based on such

¹⁰⁸ Such a conception of welfare provisioning of course resonates with discourses in social-ecological economics on more localised and place-bound “provisioning systems” (Fanning et al., 2020), see for instance Bärnthaler et al. (2021), Cato (2017), Curtis (2003), and Trainer (2020).

considerations, it has been the aim of this thesis to ground the issue of growth dependence in a Marxist understanding of the political economy of capitalism. To conclude this thesis, I would like to expand on this line of argumentation even a bit further by discussing how moving beyond growth will ultimately require substantial changes in terms of the social relations of capitalism.

From a Marxist perspective, it is clear that a post-growth society must by definition be post-capitalist (Blauwhof, 2012; Harvey, 2010; Lange, 2018; Li, 2007; Smith, 2010). Or as Magdoff & Foster (2011, p. 42) maintain, “no-growth capitalism is an oxymoron”. To discuss the overcoming of the growth imperative is thus to discuss the overcoming of capitalism as a socioeconomic system. But what would it actually entail to overcome capitalism? A good starting point for such a discussion is to comprehend capitalism as a system of social relations (Streeck, 2011). Based on this assertion, Cahen-Fourot (2022, p. 13, emphasis in original) defines capitalism “as the socio-economic organization emerging from the *generalization, the combination and the dominance* of the market relation and the wage relation”. It follows that a post-growth transformation ultimately requires a fundamental restructuring of the two constitutive social relations that underlie the capitalist system.

Employing a Polanyian perspective, Cahen-Fourot (2022) maintains that an alteration of capitalist social relations may require a large-scale decommodification of our society. In that regard, a post-growth transformation implies that the market can no longer serve as the primary institution governing the allocation and distribution of resources in society. Rather, significant parts of the economy would need to be organised outside the competitive and profit-driven logic of the market and directed first and foremost at the (sustainable) satisfaction of basic needs¹⁰⁹ (Cahen-Fourot, 2022; Li, 2007; Pirgmaier & Steinberger, 2019). Further transformative changes would pertain to the sphere of work. Here, Blauwhof (2012, p. 259) maintains that an intervention in the process of capital accumulation would in essence require an alteration of “the exploitative social relations in the workplace that makes this process possible to begin with”. Here, too, a decommodification of labour in its character as a “fictitious commodity” (Polanyi, 2001) may be indispensable (Barth et al., 2019). This, in turn, may imply a large-scale abolition of current forms of wage labour and a transformation towards a post-work society (Frayne, 2016; Gorz, 1997; Hoffmann & Paulsen, 2020; Weeks, 2011).

¹⁰⁹ The large-scale provisioning of Universal Basic Services (UBS) by the welfare state may be a well-suited measure for that purpose (Bohnenberger, 2020; Coote, 2021; Coote et al., 2019; Gough, 2019).

From this perspective, it seems that realising a post-growth society must entail going beyond the social relations of capitalism that currently lock us in a socially and ecologically pernicious path of development. The deleterious consequences that may arise from an economic system centred around a supposedly self-adjusting market and a society subject to extensive commodification have already been foreseen by Karl Polanyi (2001) in his magnum opus *The great transformation*. Here, Polanyi (2001, p. 44) writes:

“Machine production in a commercial society involves, in effect, no less a transformation than that of the natural and human substance of society into commodities. The conclusion, though weird, is inevitable; nothing less will serve the purpose: obviously, the dislocation caused by such devices must disjoint man's relationships and threaten his natural habitat with annihilation”.

To tackle the social-ecological crises with which humanity finds itself confronted, nothing less fundamental than a wholesale decommodification of the current market economy may be necessary to re-embed economic processes in the social and environmental fabric of our societies. Indeed, a “large-scale decommodification may be our best option for a post-growth transition” (Gerber & Gerber, 2017, p. 551).

I would like to end this thesis with reference to the great political economist John Stuart Mill who – more than 170 years ago – already entertained the notion of a non-growing economy. His account of the stationary state is still of surprising relevance today. Mill (2004, p. 191) writes:

“If the earth must lose that great portion of its pleasantness which it owes to things that the unlimited increase of wealth and population would extirpate from it, for the mere purpose of enabling it to support a larger, but not a better or a happier population, I sincerely hope, for the sake of posterity, that they will be content to be stationary, long before necessity compels them to it”.

If one thing stands clear at the end of this thesis, it is that necessity is upon us. And the necessity is of such that it not only compels us to be stationary; it compels us to embark on a radical transformation beyond growth and beyond capitalism.

8 Bibliography

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9 Appendix

9.1 Methodological notes on the calculation of Austria's welfare state funding composition

In order to investigate the tax base composition of welfare state funding in Austria, I have combined data by Statistik Austria (2021) on the funding of the Austrian welfare state and National Tax List data for Austria provided by Eurostat (2022). Here, the necessary calculation steps are discussed in detail.

First, I use Statistik Austria data to compute the composition of Austria's social protection receipts, yielding the relative shares of social contributions, taxes, and other receipts (see table 3).

Table 3: Composition of Austria's social protection receipts, 1995-2020

Year	Social protection receipts (in mio €)				Source of receipts in % of total social protection receipts		
	Social contributions	Taxes	Other receipts	Total social protection receipts	Social contributions	Taxes	Other receipts
1995	32,740.26	17,869.01	429.56	51,038.83	64.1	35.0	0.8
1996	34,085.43	18,059.72	440.43	52,585.59	64.8	34.3	0.8
1997	35,059.42	17,946.35	485.93	53,491.70	65.5	33.5	0.9
1998	36,218.58	18,489.50	575.21	55,283.29	65.5	33.4	1.0
1999	37,698.58	19,582.08	510.64	57,791.31	65.2	33.9	0.9
2000	38,840.04	19,742.51	705.01	59,287.55	65.5	33.3	1.2
2001	40,265.48	20,504.76	1,050.07	61,820.31	65.1	33.2	1.7
2002	40,777.57	21,995.56	1,009.17	63,782.29	63.9	34.5	1.6
2003	41,578.93	23,060.46	1,077.49	65,716.89	63.3	35.1	1.6
2004	43,030.52	23,835.18	824.81	67,690.51	63.6	35.2	1.2
2005	44,753.43	24,399.63	997.11	70,150.17	63.8	34.8	1.4
2006	46,627.97	25,380.18	908.37	72,916.53	63.9	34.8	1.2
2007	48,599.10	26,145.93	918.04	75,663.08	64.2	34.6	1.2
2008	51,416.06	27,462.24	1,152.51	80,030.81	64.2	34.3	1.4
2009	52,050.80	29,927.91	1,337.27	83,315.98	62.5	35.9	1.6
2010	53,088.02	31,157.00	1,433.74	85,678.76	62.0	36.4	1.7
2011	55,372.65	31,920.07	1,375.96	88,668.68	62.4	36.0	1.6
2012	57,223.52	33,909.92	1,345.39	92,478.83	61.9	36.7	1.5
2013	59,470.60	34,493.65	1,541.44	95,505.68	62.3	36.1	1.6
2014	61,032.79	36,201.50	1,260.20	98,494.49	62.0	36.8	1.3
2015	63,077.31	37,111.23	1,247.64	101,436.17	62.2	36.6	1.2
2016	65,150.37	38,442.66	1,408.58	105,001.61	62.0	36.6	1.3
2017	67,720.03	37,868.16	1,369.01	106,957.20	63.3	35.4	1.3

2018	69,840.69	39,749.46	1,597.21	111,187.36	62.8	35.7	1.4
2019	72,661.99	41,262.99	1,432.53	115,357.51	63.0	35.8	1.2
2020	72,009.74	46,758.58	1,526.32	120,294.63	59.9	38.9	1.3

Note: Own calculations. The values reported as 'taxes' here are originally indicated as general government contributions in the data. I do, however, assume them to be equivalent to tax revenues, since the general government contributions stem from Austria's general budget and thus consist mostly of tax revenues. Data source: Statistik Austria (2021)

In a second step, I use Eurostat's National Tax List data for Austria to illuminate how much the individual tax bases contribute to total tax revenues and total social contribution revenues, respectively. This yields the tax base composition of social contribution revenues¹¹⁰ (table 4) and the tax base composition of tax revenues (table 5).

Table 4: Tax base composition of social contribution revenue, 1995-2020

Year	Social contribution revenue (in mio €)				Total social contribution revenue	Source of revenue in % of total social contribution revenue			
	Labour	Capital	Consumption	Land		Labour	Capital	Consumption	Land
1995	25,181.53	802.57	0.00	0.00	25,984.10	96.9	3.1	0.0	0.0
1996	25,999.76	904.98	0.00	0.00	26,904.74	96.6	3.4	0.0	0.0
1997	26,688.41	1,040.99	0.00	0.00	27,729.40	96.2	3.8	0.0	0.0
1998	27,555.38	1,127.39	0.00	0.00	28,682.77	96.1	3.9	0.0	0.0
1999	28,507.85	1,179.77	0.00	0.00	29,687.62	96.0	4.0	0.0	0.0
2000	29,293.62	1,216.49	0.00	0.00	30,510.11	96.0	4.0	0.0	0.0
2001	30,101.41	1,309.09	0.00	0.00	31,410.51	95.8	4.2	0.0	0.0
2002	30,553.77	1,321.27	0.00	0.00	31,875.04	95.9	4.1	0.0	0.0
2003	31,250.58	1,418.38	0.00	0.00	32,668.96	95.7	4.3	0.0	0.0
2004	31,889.07	2,076.54	0.00	0.00	33,965.61	93.9	6.1	0.0	0.0
2005	33,188.93	2,119.48	0.00	0.00	35,308.40	94.0	6.0	0.0	0.0
2006	34,559.27	2,267.60	0.00	0.00	36,826.87	93.8	6.2	0.0	0.0
2007	36,120.97	2,332.00	0.00	0.00	38,452.96	93.9	6.1	0.0	0.0
2008	37,806.42	2,359.68	0.00	0.00	40,166.11	94.1	5.9	0.0	0.0
2009	38,154.29	2,478.10	0.00	0.00	40,632.39	93.9	6.1	0.0	0.0
2010	39,107.61	2,315.14	0.00	0.00	41,422.75	94.4	5.6	0.0	0.0

¹¹⁰ It should be noted that the extent of social contributions reported by Statistik Austria (table 3) differs significantly from the total social contribution revenue reported by Eurostat (table 4), as their respective calculation is based on different methodological procedures. Statistik Austria's data on social protection receipts is based on the European System of Integrated Social Protection Statistics (ESSPROS), while Eurostat's data builds on the European system of accounts (ESA) 2010. There are two notable differences that help to *partially* explain the discrepancy pertaining to the extent of social contributions. First, both farms' and employers' contribution to the family equalization fund (*Familienlastenausgleichsfond*) are considered to be social contributions by Statistik Austria, while they are categorised as taxes by Eurostat (see ESA 2010 code D29A and D29C in table 8). Secondly, in contrast to Eurostat data, Statistik Austria data also comprises two social protection systems, which are, strictly speaking, not state-organised but are nonetheless financed through social contributions: occupational pension schemes (*Betriebliche Pensionsvorsorge*) and employer's continued payment of wages in the event of illness (*Arbeitgeberlohnfortzahlung bei Krankheit*).

2011	40,755.36	2,593.39	0.00	0.00	43,348.75	94.0	6.0	0.0	0.0
2012	42,244.73	2,672.69	0.00	0.00	44,917.43	94.0	6.0	0.0	0.0
2013	44,016.48	2,828.95	0.00	0.00	46,845.43	94.0	6.0	0.0	0.0
2014	45,319.81	2,988.55	0.00	0.00	48,308.36	93.8	6.2	0.0	0.0
2015	46,718.88	3,147.68	0.00	0.00	49,866.56	93.7	6.3	0.0	0.0
2016	48,594.93	3,232.40	0.00	0.00	51,827.33	93.8	6.2	0.0	0.0
2017	50,483.00	3,434.90	0.00	0.00	53,917.90	93.6	6.4	0.0	0.0
2018	53,070.40	3,600.86	0.00	0.00	56,671.26	93.6	6.4	0.0	0.0
2019	55,256.92	3,819.89	0.00	0.00	59,076.82	93.5	6.5	0.0	0.0
2020	55,252.60	3,555.59	0.00	0.00	58,808.19	94.0	6.0	0.0	0.0

Note: Own calculations. Data source: Eurostat (2022)

Table 5: Tax base composition of tax revenue, 1995-2020

Year	Tax revenue (in mio €)					Source of revenue in % of total tax revenue			
	Labour	Capital	Consumption	Land	Total tax revenue	Labour	Capital	Consumption	Land
1995	16,583.82	9,832.70	20,653.07	400.39	47,469.98	34.9	20.7	43.5	0.8
1996	17,414.98	11,568.83	22,108.92	414.46	51,507.19	33.8	22.5	42.9	0.8
1997	19,149.60	11,808.81	23,453.50	425.57	54,837.48	34.9	21.5	42.8	0.8
1998	19,958.78	12,516.47	24,300.29	437.63	57,213.18	34.9	21.9	42.5	0.8
1999	20,994.27	11,857.00	25,430.28	455.95	58,737.50	35.7	20.2	43.3	0.8
2000	21,267.18	12,632.30	26,036.75	467.74	60,403.97	35.2	20.9	43.1	0.8
2001	22,295.49	16,277.91	26,755.94	484.59	65,813.92	33.9	24.7	40.7	0.7
2002	23,202.09	13,891.19	27,782.09	495.36	65,370.74	35.5	21.2	42.5	0.8
2003	24,100.76	13,365.57	28,124.53	515.48	66,106.34	36.5	20.2	42.5	0.8
2004	24,128.26	14,279.72	29,270.28	528.01	68,206.26	35.4	20.9	42.9	0.8
2005	24,111.69	14,633.17	30,116.72	543.84	69,405.42	34.7	21.1	43.4	0.8
2006	25,628.54	15,081.80	30,618.57	549.12	71,878.03	35.7	21.0	42.6	0.8
2007	27,235.43	17,145.47	32,201.82	560.66	77,143.39	35.3	22.2	41.7	0.7
2008	29,632.98	18,223.71	33,424.22	584.31	81,865.21	36.2	22.3	40.8	0.7
2009	28,398.80	15,263.17	33,594.07	599.85	77,855.89	36.5	19.6	43.1	0.8
2010	29,355.70	15,879.61	34,341.23	615.01	80,191.55	36.6	19.8	42.8	0.8
2011	30,999.81	17,030.69	35,858.99	626.49	84,515.98	36.7	20.2	42.4	0.7
2012	33,114.41	17,597.12	37,153.24	638.62	88,503.39	37.4	19.9	42.0	0.7
2013	34,262.85	19,016.95	37,657.52	657.17	91,594.49	37.4	20.8	41.1	0.7
2014	35,903.06	19,177.69	38,511.43	665.13	94,257.31	38.1	20.3	40.9	0.7
2015	37,419.55	21,095.56	39,702.33	680.37	98,897.81	37.8	21.3	40.1	0.7
2016	34,704.19	21,201.02	41,112.37	690.26	97,707.85	35.5	21.7	42.1	0.7
2017	35,258.89	22,275.54	42,722.54	708.82	100,965.78	34.9	22.1	42.3	0.7
2018	37,399.73	24,476.11	43,777.32	724.49	106,377.65	35.2	23.0	41.2	0.7
2019	38,983.29	25,498.02	45,168.29	730.03	110,379.63	35.3	23.1	40.9	0.7
2020	37,138.28	20,947.80	41,868.30	749.98	100,704.36	36.9	20.8	41.6	0.7

Note: Own calculations. Data source: Eurostat (2022)

In a third step, the tax base shares of table 4 and 5 are transposed to the Statistik Austria data presented in table 3. This yields the tax base composition of Austria's social protection receipts, covering both social contributions and taxes separately¹¹¹. We thus arrive at the results presented in table 6, which is equivalent to table 3 but further includes the respective tax base compositions. To illustrate the calculation procedure employed, let us take the example of labour social contributions in % of total social protection receipts for 1995 (table 6). Here, I multiply the share of social contribution receipts in % of total social protection receipts (table 3) with the share of labour in % of total social contribution revenue (table 4), i.e. $64.1 * 0.969 \approx 62.2$.

Table 6: Social contributions, taxes, and other receipts by source in % of total social protection receipts, 1995-2020

Year	Social contributions by source in % of total social protection receipts				Taxes by source in % of total social protection receipts				Other receipts in % of total social protection receipts
	Labour	Capital	Consumption	Land	Labour	Capital	Consumption	Land	
1995	62.2	2.0	0.0	0.0	12.2	7.3	15.2	0.3	0.8
1996	62.6	2.2	0.0	0.0	11.6	7.7	14.7	0.3	0.8
1997	63.1	2.5	0.0	0.0	11.7	7.2	14.3	0.3	0.9
1998	62.9	2.6	0.0	0.0	11.7	7.3	14.2	0.3	1.0
1999	62.6	2.6	0.0	0.0	12.1	6.8	14.7	0.3	0.9
2000	62.9	2.6	0.0	0.0	11.7	7.0	14.4	0.3	1.2
2001	62.4	2.7	0.0	0.0	11.2	8.2	13.5	0.2	1.7
2002	61.3	2.7	0.0	0.0	12.2	7.3	14.7	0.3	1.6
2003	60.5	2.7	0.0	0.0	12.8	7.1	14.9	0.3	1.6
2004	59.7	3.9	0.0	0.0	12.5	7.4	15.1	0.3	1.2
2005	60.0	3.8	0.0	0.0	12.1	7.3	15.1	0.3	1.4
2006	60.0	3.9	0.0	0.0	12.4	7.3	14.8	0.3	1.2
2007	60.3	3.9	0.0	0.0	12.2	7.7	14.4	0.3	1.2
2008	60.5	3.8	0.0	0.0	12.4	7.6	14.0	0.2	1.4
2009	58.7	3.8	0.0	0.0	13.1	7.0	15.5	0.3	1.6
2010	58.5	3.5	0.0	0.0	13.3	7.2	15.6	0.3	1.7
2011	58.7	3.7	0.0	0.0	13.2	7.3	15.3	0.3	1.6
2012	58.2	3.7	0.0	0.0	13.7	7.3	15.4	0.3	1.5
2013	58.5	3.8	0.0	0.0	13.5	7.5	14.8	0.3	1.6
2014	58.1	3.8	0.0	0.0	14.0	7.5	15.0	0.3	1.3
2015	58.3	3.9	0.0	0.0	13.8	7.8	14.7	0.3	1.2

¹¹¹ Crucially, this step builds on the assumption that the tax base composition of both tax revenues and social contribution revenues derived from Austria's National Tax List data is applicable to the data on social protection receipts by Statistik Austria.

2016	58.2	3.9	0.0	0.0	13.0	7.9	15.4	0.3	1.3
2017	59.3	4.0	0.0	0.0	12.4	7.8	15.0	0.2	1.3
2018	58.8	4.0	0.0	0.0	12.6	8.2	14.7	0.2	1.4
2019	58.9	4.1	0.0	0.0	12.6	8.3	14.6	0.2	1.2
2020	56.2	3.6	0.0	0.0	14.3	8.1	16.2	0.3	1.3

Note: Own calculations. Data sources: Eurostat (2022) & Statistik Austria (2021)

In the last step, the respective tax base shares pertaining to taxes and social contributions are added up. This yields the composition of welfare state funding in Austria (table 7). The table contains the same data that is depicted in figure 3, presented in section 5.1.1.

Table 7: Composition of welfare state funding by source in % of total social protection receipts, 1995-2020

Year	Social contributions plus taxes by source in % of total social protection receipts				Other receipts in % of total social protection receipts
	Labour	Capital	Consumption	Land	Other receipts
1995	74.4	9.2	15.2	0.3	0.8
1996	74.3	9.9	14.7	0.3	0.8
1997	74.8	9.7	14.3	0.3	0.9
1998	74.6	9.9	14.2	0.3	1.0
1999	74.8	9.4	14.7	0.3	0.9
2000	74.6	9.6	14.4	0.3	1.2
2001	73.7	10.9	13.5	0.2	1.7
2002	73.5	10.0	14.7	0.3	1.6
2003	73.3	9.8	14.9	0.3	1.6
2004	72.1	11.3	15.1	0.3	1.2
2005	72.1	11.2	15.1	0.3	1.4
2006	72.4	11.2	14.8	0.3	1.2
2007	72.5	11.6	14.4	0.3	1.2
2008	72.9	11.4	14.0	0.2	1.4
2009	71.8	10.9	15.5	0.3	1.6
2010	71.8	10.7	15.6	0.3	1.7
2011	71.9	11.0	15.3	0.3	1.6
2012	71.9	11.0	15.4	0.3	1.5
2013	72.0	11.3	14.8	0.3	1.6
2014	72.1	11.3	15.0	0.3	1.3
2015	72.1	11.7	14.7	0.3	1.2
2016	71.2	11.8	15.4	0.3	1.3
2017	71.6	11.8	15.0	0.2	1.3
2018	71.4	12.2	14.7	0.2	1.4
2019	71.5	12.3	14.6	0.2	1.2
2020	70.6	11.7	16.2	0.3	1.3

Note: Own calculations. Data sources: Eurostat (2022) & Statistik Austria (2021)

9.2 Tax base allocation of taxes and social contributions in Austria

The following two tables show the tax base allocation of individual types of taxes and social contributions in Austria, respectively. Note that the following taxes and social contributions have been omitted from the analysis and are thus not displayed in the tables below: taxes and social contributions with a reported value of zero; taxes and social contributions with no data available; voluntary households' actual social contributions (ESA 2010 code D613V); imputed social contributions (ESA 2010 code D612); and lastly capital transfers from general government to relevant sectors representing taxes and social contributions assessed but unlikely to be collected (ESA 2010 code D995).

Moreover, a short note on personal income taxes is necessary here. Income taxes usually cover income from various sources. Hence, country-specific methodologies have been developed to split the income tax between capital and labour for each year¹¹². In the case of Austria, “the split of the personal income tax was estimated by the Ministry of Finance using statistical information from the wage withholding tax and the final income tax by assessment” (European Commission & Directorate-General for Taxation and Customs Union, 2022b, p. 332). Thus, table 8 contains a fifth tax base category named ‘Split’. Further information and the exact split for Austria can be found in annex B of the publication *Taxation trends in the European Union: data for the EU Member States, Iceland, Norway: 2022 edition* (European Commission & Directorate-General for Taxation and Customs Union, 2022b).

Table 8: Tax base allocation for taxes in Austria

ESA 2010 code	Tax name according to national classification (in German)	Tax name according to national classification (in English)	Tax base allocation
D211	Mehrwertsteuer	Value added tax	Consumption
D211	MwSt - Unterkompensation, Landwirtschaft	Under-compensation of VAT (flat rate system), agriculture	Consumption
D211	EU-Umsatzsteuer-One-Stop-Shop (MOSS)	Value added tax from VAT-Mini-One-Stop-Shop (MOSS)	Consumption
D2121	Sonstige Einfuhrabgaben	Other import duties	Consumption
D2121	Zölle	Customs duties	Consumption

¹¹² Note that I have added land as a fourth tax base category for the purpose of my analysis, which too acts as a source of income. Being based on the tripartite tax base category employed by Eurostat (2022), the split methodology applied in the National Tax List does not include land as a separate source of income. This of course might indicate an underestimation of land’s contribution and an overestimation of capital’s contribution to financing the Austrian welfare state, respectively.

D2122A	Importausgleichsbeiträge gemäß MOG	Import equalization duties	Consumption
D2122C	"Rotterdam" Zuschlag	Import duties not collected on the national border	Consumption
D2122E	Außenhandelsförderungsbeitrag	Contribution to promote foreign trade	Consumption
D214A	Absatzförderungsbeitrag auf Milch	Duty promotion milk distribution	Consumption
D214A	Alkoholsteuer	Duty on spirit	Consumption
D214A	Sonderabgabe auf alkoholische Getränke	Special duty on alcoholic drinks	Consumption
D214A	Agrarmarkt Austria	Contribution to the Agricultural Fund	Consumption
D214A	Biersteuer	Tax on beer	Consumption
D214A	Energieabgabe	Tax on energy	Consumption
D214A	Getränksteuer	Beverage tax	Consumption
D214A	Zusatzabgabe Milchquotenüberschreitung	Duty on exceeding milk-quota	Consumption
D214A	Mineralölsteuer	Tax on mineral oils	Consumption
D214A	Normverbrauchsabgabe	Duty on vehicles based on fuel consumption	Consumption
D214A	Sonstige Einnahmen gemäß MOG	Other receipts - Market Organisation Act	Consumption
D214A	Schaumweinsteuer	Tax on sparkling wine	Consumption
D214A	Sonderabgabe von Erdölprodukten	Special tax on mineral oils	Consumption
D214A	Abgabe auf Stärkeerzeugnisse	Duty on starch products	Consumption
D214A	Tabaksteuer	Tax on tobacco	Consumption
D214A	Weinsteuer	Tax on wine	Consumption
D214A	Zuckerabgabe	Levy on sugar	Consumption
D214C	Grunderwerbsteuer	Land transfer tax	Capital
D214C	Kapitalverkehrssteuern	Capital transfer tax	Capital
D214D	Kraftfahrzeugzulassungssteuer	Car registration taxes	Consumption
D214E	Lustbarkeitsabgabe	Entertainment tax	Consumption
D214E	Vergnügungssteuer	Amusement tax	Consumption
D214F	Gewinnsteuer	Tax on gambling stakes 2	Consumption
D214F	Konzessionsabgabe	Tax on gambling stakes 1	Consumption
D214F	Spielbankenabgabe	Duty on casinos	Consumption
D214G	Feuerschutzsteuer	Fire protection tax	Consumption
D214G	Versicherungssteuer	Insurance tax	Consumption
D214H	Altlastenbeitrag	Levy on dangerous waste	Consumption
D214H	Ankündigungsabgabe	Announcement tax	Consumption
D214H	Anzeigenabgabe	Advertisement tax	Consumption
D214H	Fremdenverkehrsabgabe	Tax on tourism	Consumption
D214H	Sicherheitsabgabe / Zivilluftfahrt	Duty for airways security	Consumption
D214H	Werbeabgabe	Tax on advertisement	Consumption
D214H	Digitalsteuer auf Onlinewerbeleistungen	Tax on online advertisement	Consumption
D214H	Flugabgabe	Flight Charge	Consumption
D214J	Gewinne, Branntweinmonopol	Federal monopolies, spirits	Consumption
D214J	Gewinne, Glückspielmonopol	Federal monopolies, gambling	Consumption
D214L	Beiträge an den Künstler-Sozialversicherungsfonds	Contribution to the artists' social security fund	Consumption

D29A	Abgabe von land-und forstwirtschaftlichen Betrieben	Duty on farms	Capital
D29A	Beiträge von land- und forstwirtschaft. Betrieben zum AFFB/FLAF	Farm's contribution to the family equalization fund (FLAF)	Capital
D29A	Bodenwertabgabe	Tax on vacant plots	Land
D29A	Grundsteuer A	Real estate tax A (farm land)	Land
D29A	Grundsteuer B	Real estate tax (except farm land)	Land
D29A	Kammerbeiträge, Landwirtschaftskammer	Contribution to Chamber of Agriculture	Capital
D29C	Dienstgeberbeiträge zum AFFB/FLAF	Employer contribution to the family equalization fund (FLAF)	Labour
D29C	Invalidenausgleichstaxfonds	Disabled persons, equalization levy	Labour
D29C	Kammerbeiträge	Contribution to chambers	Labour
D29C	Kommunalsteuer	Tax on sum of wages	Labour
D29C	U-Bahnabgabe	Tax on employment (Vienna underground)	Labour
D29F	Emissionszertifikate	Emission trading allowances	Consumption
D29G	MwSt - Unterkompensation, Landwirtschaft	Under-compensation of VAT (flat rate system), agriculture	Consumption
D29H	Gebrauchsabgabe	Certain users fee	Capital
D29H	Kraftfahrzeugsteuer	Motor vehicles tax	Capital
D29H	Motorbezogene Versicherungssteuer, Anteil Unternehmen	Engine-specific insurance tax, paid by enterprises	Capital
D29H	Abgabenstrafen und Resteingänge sonstiger weggefallener Steuern	Fines related to tax offences, taxes on production and imports	Capital
D29H	Punzierungskontrollgebühr	Embossment fee	Capital
D29H	Sonstige Abgaben	Other taxes, taxes on production n.e.c.	Capital
D29H	In Stempelmarken entrichtete Gebühren	Stamp fees	Capital
D29H	Straßenbenützungabgabe (Straßenverkehrsbeitrag)	Road transport duty	Capital
D29H	Übrige Gebühren (ohne Gewinnstgebühr)	Other fees, taxes on production n.e.c.	Capital
D29H	Abgaben an den Verkehrssicherheitsfonds, Anteil Unternehmen	Contribution to the Road Safety Fund, paid by enterprises	Capital
D29H	Verwaltungsabgaben	Administration duties	Capital
D29H	Stabilitätsabgabe	Financial Institutions Stability Fee	Capital
D29H	Haftungsentgelte Bund	Liability remuneration	Capital
D29H	Kunst-/Kulturförderungsbeitrag, Anteil Unternehmen	Contribution for the promotion of arts, paid by enterprises	Consumption
D29H	Rundfunkgebühren, Anteil Unternehmen	Broadcasting fees, paid by enterprises	Consumption
D29H	ORF-Programmentgelt, Anteil Unternehmen	Programming fees of public service broadcasting, paid by enterprises	Consumption
D29H	Beiträge an Single Resolution Fund (EU)	Contributions to Single Resolution Fund (EU)	Capital
D29H	Zahlungen an Einlagensicherungsfonds	Deposit guarantee schemes (DGS) payments	Capital

D29H	Ausgleichsabgabe nach dem Wiener Baumschutzgesetz	Compensation levy according to the Vienna Tree Protection Act	Capital
D51A	Veranlagte Einkommensteuer	Income tax	Split
D51A	EU Quellensteuer	EU withholding tax on interest income of non-residents	Capital
D51A	Gewerbsteuer	Tax on industry and trade	Capital
D51A	Kammerbeiträge (Anteil Arbeitnehmer)	Contribution to chambers (Employees)	Labour
D51A	Kammerbeiträge (Anteil Selbständige)	Contribution to chambers (Self-employed)	Capital
D51A	Kapitalertragsteuer	Tax on capital yields	Capital
D51A	Kapitalertragsteuer auf Zinsen	Tax on interest	Capital
D51A	Lohnsteuer	Wage tax	Split
D51B	Gewerbsteuer	Tax on industry and trade	Capital
D51B	Kammerbeiträge	Contribution to chambers	Capital
D51B	Kapitalertragsteuer	Tax on capital yields	Capital
D51B	Kapitalertragsteuer auf Zinsen	Tax on interest	Capital
D51B	Körperschaftsteuer	Corporation tax	Capital
D51E	Abgabe von Zuwendungen an politische Parteien	Duty on contributions to political parties	Capital
D51E	Sonderabgabe von Kreditunternehmungen	Special levy on banks (historic)	Capital
D51E	Wohnbauförderungsbeitrag (Anteil Arbeitnehmer)	Promotion residential buildings - Employees	Labour
D51E	Wohnbauförderungsbeitrag (Anteil Arbeitgeber)	Promotion residential buildings - Employers	Labour
D59A	Erbschaftsteueräquivalent	Capital death duty	Capital
D59A	Vermögensteuer	Capital tax	Capital
D59A	Zweitwohnsitzabgabe	Tax on secondary residences	Capital
D59F	Kunst-/Kulturförderungsbeitrag, Anteil private Haushalte	Contribution for the promotion of arts, paid by households	Consumption
D59F	Rundfunkgebühren, Anteil private Haushalte	Broadcasting fees, paid by households	Consumption
D59F	Jagd- und Fischereiabgabe	Hunting and fishing duties	Consumption
D59F	Hochschülerschaftsbeiträge	Contributions to students' association	Labour
D59F	Abgabe für das Halten von Tieren	Dog tax	Consumption
D59F	Motorbezogene Versicherungssteuer, Anteil private Haushalte	Engine-specific insurance tax, paid by households	Consumption
D59F	Abgabenstrafen und Resteingänge sonstiger weggefallener Steuern	Fines related to tax offences, taxes on income, wealth etc.	Capital
D59F	Sonstige Abgaben	Other taxes	Consumption
D59F	In Stempelmarken entrichtete Gebühren	Stamp fees	Capital
D59F	Übrige Gebühren (ohne Gewinngebühr)	Other fees	Consumption
D59F	Abgaben an den Verkehrssicherheitsfonds, Anteil private Haushalte	Contribution to the Road Safety Fund, paid by households	Consumption
D59F	Verwaltungsabgaben	Administration duties	Consumption

D59F	ORF-Programmengelt, Anteil private Haushalte	Programming fees of public service broadcasting, paid by households	Consumption
D91A	Erbschaft- und Schenkungssteuer	Estate, inheritance and gift tax	Capital
D91A	Stiftungseingangssteuer	Foundation Tax	Capital
D91B	Abgeltungssteuer	Withholding Tax	Capital

Note: Own representation. Data source: Eurostat (2022)

Table 9: Tax base allocation for social contributions in Austria

ESA 2010 code	Tax name according to national classification (in German)	Tax name according to national classification (in English)	Tax base allocation
D611C	Arbeitslosenversicherungsbeiträge	Unemployment insurance contributions	Labour
D611C	Beiträge nach dem Betriebshilfegesetz	Special health insurance contributions	Labour
D611C	Beiträge zur Bauarbeiter-Urlaubs- und Abfertigungskasse (BUAK)	Special unemployment insurance contributions, construction workers	Labour
D611C	Beiträge nach dem Entgeltfortzahlungsgesetz (EFZG)	Contributions to sickness benefit fund	Labour
D611C	Beiträge nach dem Insolvenz- Ausfallgeldgesetz (IESG)	Contributions to insolvency fund	Labour
D611C	Beiträge an Krankenfürsorgeanstalten	Health insurance contributions, local government employees	Labour
D611C	Beiträge zur Krankenversicherung	Health insurance contributions	Labour
D611C	Nachtschichtschwerarbeits-Beitrag	Special pension contributions, nightshift worker	Labour
D611C	Dienstgeberbeiträge zur Pensionssicherung der Beamten	Pension contributions, civil servants	Labour
D611C	Beiträge zur Pensionsversicherung	Pension insurance contributions	Labour
D611C	Beiträge nach dem Bauarbeiter- Schlechtwetterentschädigungsgesetz	Special unemployment insurance contributions, construction workers, until 1996	Labour
D611C	Unfallversicherungsbeiträge	Accident insurance contributions	Labour
D613CE	Arbeitslosenversicherungsbeiträge	Unemployment insurance contributions	Labour
D613CE	Beiträge zur Bauarbeiter-Urlaubs- und Abfertigungskasse (BUAK)	Special unemployment insurance contributions, construction workers	Labour
D613CE	Beiträge an Krankenfürsorgeanstalten	Health insurance contributions, local government employees	Labour
D613CE	Beiträge zur Krankenversicherung	Health insurance contributions	Labour
D613CE	Pensionsbeiträge der Beamten	Pension contributions, civil servants	Labour
D613CE	Beiträge zur Pensionsversicherung	Pension insurance contributions	Labour
D613CE	Beiträge nach dem Bauarbeiter- Schlechtwetterentschädigungsgesetz	Special unemployment insurance contributions, construction workers, until 1996	Labour
D613CE	Unfallversicherungsbeiträge	Accident insurance contributions	Labour
D613CS	Beiträge zur Krankenversicherung	Health insurance contributions	Capital
D613CS	Beiträge zur Pensionsversicherung	Pension insurance contributions	Capital
D613CS	Unfallversicherungsbeiträge	Accident insurance contributions	Capital
D613CN	Beiträge zur Krankenversicherung	Health insurance contributions	Labour
D613CN	Beiträge zur Pensionsversicherung	Pension insurance contributions	Labour

D613CN	Pensionssicherungsbeiträge der Beamten im Ruhestand	Special pension contributions, civil servants (retired)	Labour
D613CN	Beiträge an Krankenfürsorgeanstalten	Health insurance contributions, local government employees	Labour

Note: Own representation. Data source: Eurostat (2022)

9.3 Complimentary graphs

Figure 4: Social protection expenditure of the Austrian welfare state by function in % of GDP, 1990-2020

Note: Own calculations. Data source: Statistik Austria (2021)

Figure 5: Composition of Austria's social protection funding by tax base in % of GDP, 1995-2020

Note: Own calculations. Data sources: Eurostat (2022) & Statistik Austria (2021)